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D.5.7 Procedures for the advanced description of paleontological and paleoanthropological specimens

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Abstract

The overall goal of WP5 is to develop key methods to address innovative and interoperable research on legacy systems as a unified process, while better building and expanding the decentralized facilities of IPERION HS. This will raise the knowledge and skills of the consortium to a higher level of excellence and contribute to RI's long-term competitiveness. The aim of the Joint Research Actions (JRA) described in this work program is to provide new research resources to all TNA platforms to provide better access services for researchers and heritage professionals across Europe. The proposed development directions follow the key research questions and scientific challenges identified in a consultation process with a wide range of heritage researchers. Such a structure allows a significant leap towards the integration of the various access rights provisions of the RI. The results will increase the sustainability of research results through cross-platform comparison, critically involving the development of interoperability between physical and digital tools, enabling the move towards a fully integrated European research infrastructure. The proposed actions take into account the expansion of the current user community. The aim is to exploit the full potential of the instrumental capabilities and documentation expertise of IPERION HS to provide innovative methods in the field of archeology and paleontology, benefiting from the further adoption and development of new methods. One example is speciation using spectral imaging, a technique that was widely developed for the study of art, although it continues to appear in paleontology and paleoanthropology.

Specific goals

WP5 implements five JRAs aimed at improving current and future access rights services. The developed solutions are available on the ARCHLAB, FIXLAB and MOLAB operating platforms and will be deployed on the future E-RIHS DIGILAB platform. The specific objectives of these five measures are:

- Develop methods and optimized tools so that RI can effectively meet the needs of preventive protection;
- Development of archaeological documentation both in the field and in the laboratory on existing data and collections;
- Optimizing and implementing analytical tracking strategies to avoid possible damage to objects during measurement under strong beams;
- Improving the heritage knowledge capabilities of platform access providers - description, accessibility, preservation, sharing, reuse - by supporting the heritage knowledge FAIR process and exploring the optimal uses of EOSC in the heritage community;
- Develop methods and optimize RI instruments to bring new imaging strategies to paleontological and paleoanthropological specimens in natural science collections.

Most of techniques are offered via the IPERION HS catalogue of services.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Expansion
MOLAB	MOBILE LABORATORY
MICRO LIBS	Micro laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy
MICRO CT	Microcomputed tomography
GE	General Electric
MCICP-MS	Multicollector Induced coupled plasma mass spectrometer
NIST	National Institute of Standards and technology
IRMM	Certified material from the certified reference materials catalogue of the Joint Research Centre
MINECO	Ministerio de Asuntos Económicos y Transformación Digital (Spain)
3D MODEL	Three dimensional model
TBR	Three bisectonal Reconnection
CT SCANS	Micro CT scan
MED CT	Medical CT
ESR	Electron Spin Resonance
EPR	Electron Paramagnetic Resonance
FTIR SPECTROM	Fourier-transform infrared <i>spectroscopy</i>
ICP AES	Induced coupled plasma atomic emission spectrometry
ICP MS	Induced coupled plasma mass spectrometer
NT	Neutron Tomography
SRMs	Standard reference materials
INAA	Instrumental Neutron Activation Analysis
PGAA	Prompt gamma activation analysis

Introduction

The benefit of connecting heritage science analytic methods and procedures to palaeontology and palaeoanthropology comes from the unique characteristics of their material systems. These materials are aged, multi-scale, heterogeneous, and culturally valuable, making them ideal for study and analysis. Because of the academic and methodological compartmentalization, different approaches have been developed separately in each sector, which could greatly benefit the other sector.

Our proposal aims to create and assess innovative imaging and spectroscopic techniques for enhanced documentation and preservation in the fields of paleontology and paleoanthropology. This will be achieved by utilizing leading-edge methods commonly employed in the analysis of art materials, and drawing on the extensive knowledge and skills of the IPERION HS distributed facilities. In the field of heritage science, methods that offer elemental characterization and speciation have the potential to greatly enhance our understanding of the preservation and interpretation of specimens. This includes providing insight into taxonomic information and constraining environmental conditions.

By taking the unique properties of paleo materials into account when considering art and archaeological materials, we can broaden the scope of instruments used in IPERION HS by making specific adjustments to the instruments and methodologies.

To try to apply new imaging and spectroscopy methods in paleontology and paleoanthropology, a series of studies have been carried out on study techniques used by heritage sciences to develop new analysis techniques for paleontological specimens. Various procedures have been performed using analysis techniques.

Methods and micro-LIBS imaging are used to analyse the elemental composition of ancient materials.

The use of various methods will enable the investigation of specimens with minimal invasiveness, while maintaining crucial anatomical information. This includes the use of X-ray spectral and digital imaging, to characterize organic materials in fossil contexts. Additionally, remote sensing methods will be employed in MOLAB for further analysis. We will develop methodologies with the goal of reducing the use of fossil materials and enhancing data quality through the correlation of experiments. Apart from examining individual specimens, the methods being developed will focus on enhancing the understanding of environmental and climatic conditions.

Activities and experiments carried out

After establishing contacts with different institutions, European projects and with the leaders of the dating and material characterization laboratories at CENIEH, with the aim of carrying out nondestructive or semi destructive analyses to answer different questions for the study of paleontological and paleoanthropological specimens.

All the samples has been selected according to the main interests of the paleontological and paleoanthropological community. Different experiments have been carried out focused on various topics, which we will develop below.

Topic 1: Direct fossil dating and Lithic tools dating to provide minimum ages

Work 1: 14C measurements on Santa Catalina petrosal bones on Santa Catalina site.

Access offered : 14C-AMS measurements. Laboratorio di Tecniche Nucleari per l' Ambiente e i Beni Culturali (INFN). Firenze, Italy.

Author: Daniel Garcia *et al.*

Sample preparation

Before any radiocarbon measurement, the sample to be dated has to be prepared in order to remove all the possible contaminations and to isolate the original carbon.

Samples	Lab. code	Material
<i>CSN'13_CEF6</i>	-	Petrosal bone
<i>CSN'13_CEF8</i>	-	Petrosal bone
<i>SCT'15_T1UF21_5005</i>	FI4767, FI4775	Petrosal bone
<i>SCT'15_T1UF21_5006</i>	Fi4763, Fi4765	Petrosal bone

Table 1 Samples fractions prepared for 14C-AMS measurements

Figure 1 Bone samples subjected to preparation.

As a first step, for each of the samples, the portion chosen for the measurement was first mechanically cleaned using a scalpel to remove the most external layers and then crushed. Since a translucent material, probably indicating the use of some consolidating product, was present on the samples, we decided to clean the selected powdered material by several extractions in chloroform before proceeding with collagen collection. Four extractions in chloroform were applied. Then, collagen was extracted following the so-called Longin method:

- complete demineralization in aqueous 0.5M HCl at room temperature for about 24 hours, at least;
- purification in aqueous 0.1M NaOH at room temperature for 2 hours;
- further bath in 1M HCl at room temperature for 2 hours to remove any CO₂ possibly absorbed from atmosphere during the previous step;
- gelatinization of the collagen-based acidified solution (pH ~3) at 80°C.

During this procedure, collagen cannot be extracted from samples *CSN'13_CEF6* and *CSN'13_CEF8*. Actually, after the pre-treatment, the two samples showed significant reddish residues (see Figure 2), which were insoluble in acidic solution (such a behaviour suggests that the original bone matrix might have replaced by other minerals).

Figure 2 Reddish residues collected after pre-treatment of samples *CSN'13_CEF6* and *CSN'13_CEF8*.

After pre-treatment, carbon was extracted from *SCT'15_T1UF21_5005* and *SCT'15_T1UF21_5006* samples as gaseous CO₂ by combustion in elemental analyser (CHN Thermo Flash1112) and then converted to graphite, i.e. solid carbon, exploiting the reaction of carbon dioxide with hydrogen (with iron as catalyst). Two separate fractions from the same cleaned sample were independently combusted and graphitised (see Table 1 for the laboratory codes).

Results

Graphite pellets were measured by Accelerator Mass Spectrometry (AMS) at the dedicated beam line of the Tandem accelerator at INFN-LABEC laboratory in Florence.

Work 2: Dating results for Palaeolithic stone tools using uranium - thorium series

Access offered : Uranium Series Lab. Research Center on Human Evolution (CENIEH). Burgos, Spain.

Author: Fernando Jiménez et lab.

1. Introduction.

Dating of four adhered crusts of siliceous rock and one calcareous rock is requested using uranium series analysis. The pieces are received on December 17, 2020, with the following coding.

ID	Aprox. quantity	Type of sample
TOR 20PR - 4000	g	Heterogeneous crust adhered to siliceous rock (quartzite)
TOR 20PR - 4001	g	Heterogeneous crust adhered to siliceous rock (quartzite)
TOR 20PR - 4002	g	Heterogeneous crust adhered to siliceous rock (quartzite)
TOR 20PR - 4003	g	Heterogeneous crust adhered to siliceous rock (quartzite)
TOR 20PR - 0001	g	Stalagmite slice with visible lamination

Table 2: samples coding

Some images of the samples and the location of the points selected for analysis:

Sample TOR 20-Pr-4000

Figure 3 Amygdaloid biface with a patina of carbonate 7x4 cm

Description

Identification in laboratory: SU-2020-247-3

It is an amygdaloid biface type quartzite artifact measuring about 7x4 cm with a patina of carbonate material that can be analyzed to try to date it using uranium series.

The crust has low consistency and no lamellar structure is observed, while a certain porosity is sensed.

The following images show the complete specimen and details of the patina. The yellowish appearance with darker parts can be observed, suggesting the presence of components other than CaCO_3 , which are avoided as far as possible.

Sampling was carried out on the carbonate layer of the photograph, after removing the superficial part, taking a small amount without touching the biface.

Figure 4 Amygdaloid biface with a patina of carbonate 7x4 cm

Figure 5 Amygdaloid biface with a patina of carbonate 7x4 cm

Sample TOR 20-Pr-4001

Description

Identification in laboratory: SU-2020-247-4

It is an amygdaloid biface type quartzite artifact measuring about 10x5 cm with a patina of carbonate material that can be analyzed to try to date it using uranium series.

The following images show the complete specimen and details of the patina. The scab has low consistency and no lamellar structure is observed, and the yellowish appearance with darker parts can be observed, suggesting the presence of components other than CaCO_3 , which are avoided as much as possible.

Sampling was carried out on the carbonate layer of the photograph, after removing the superficial part, taking a small amount without touching the biface.

Figure 6 Amygdaloid biface 10x5 cm

Figure 7 Amygdaloid biface 10x5 cm

Figure 8 Amygdaloid biface 10x5 cm

Sample TOR 20-Pr-4002

Description

Identification in laboratory: SU-2020-247-1

It is a quartzite flake measuring about 6x4 cm, with a carbonate crust attached. The thickness of this scab is variable, and can reach just over 1 mm in the thickest part.

The scab was sampled again after removing the most superficial part.

Figure 9 Quartzite flake measuring about 6x4 cm

Figure 10 Quartzite flake measuring 6x4 cm

Figure 11 Quartzite flake measuring about 6x4 cm

Sample TOR 20-Pr-4003

Description

Identification in laboratory: SU-2020-247-2

It is a quartzite core measuring about 3x3 cm with a yellowish crust and numerous black and red particles. The thickness reaches 1 mm in some places, although the appearance is quite heterogeneous.

Figure 12 Quartzite core

Figure 13. Quartzite core

Figure 14. Quartzite core

Sample TOR 20-Pr-0001**Description****Identification in laboratory: SU-2020-247-5**

This sample is a fragment of stalagmite. When cutting it, the evolution of this specimen is clearly observed.

For sampling, the central part of the stalagmite is avoided, taking the carbonate from the furthest part possible, as indicated by the arrow in the following photograph, and avoiding extracting carbonate from the most porous parts and those close to the edges.

Figure 15 Fragment of stalagmite

The laboratory coding is as follows:

User ID	Lab ID	Clean Lab ID
TOR20-PR-4000	20205-3	SU-477
TOR20-PR-4001	20205-4	SU-478
TOR20-PR-4002	20205-1	SU-475
TOR20-PR-4003	20205-2	SU-476
TOR20-PR-0001	20205-5	SU-479

Table 3 Laboratory samples coding

Each of the specimens is subsampled, using a manual tungsten carbide bur, 0.8 mm in diameter. First, the most superficial part of the sampling area was removed with the drill itself, discarding it, and then an amount of between 10-50 mg of material was extracted, avoiding reaching the quartzite.

In the stalactite, the furthest part of the growth zone, usually considered an open system, was chosen.

2. Applied methodology

PREPARATION OF SAMPLE

The sampled materials are collected in low-density plastic centrifuge tubes and treated in a metal-free clean room, where radiotracers are added, homogenized, carbonate removed, digestion and separation of the analytes of interest using resins. ion exchange, following the internal PE-06SU method.

Once the uranium and thorium fractions of each sample have been separated and purified, the isotopic ratios and elemental concentration of the solutions obtained are determined, following the internal method PE-07SU.

INSTRUMENTATION

Measurements of isotopic ratios and quantification of uranium and thorium were performed using a dual-focus magnetic sector mass spectrometer, multi-collector detector system, and plasma ionization mode generated by inductive coupling MC ICP-MS Thermo NEPTUNE .

The equipment configuration included the use of an RPQ filter and detection of ²³⁸U, ²³²Th in Faraday cups and ²³⁰Th and ²³⁴Th in addition to the spikes ²³⁶U, ²²⁹Th, in ion counters. The equipment is configured with a jet interface system with type

The measurements of isotopic ratios and uranium and thorium content were carried out in two sequences per element in static and quantification by the standard bracketing method. The concentration of ²³⁸U and ²³²Th was carried out using the isotopic dilution method (IDMS). The spikes and standards used are gravimetrically obtained dilutions of standards and certified reference materials owned by CENIEH, with direct traceability to NIST and IRMM.

The numerical results obtained are:

Table 4 Legend of the results table

Sample	Name of the sample collected.
Lab- ID	Code assigned to the collected sample.
SU-ID	Laboratory subsample code used to generate the data..
²³⁸U [μg g⁻¹]	Uranium concentration in the subsample.
²³²Th [μg g⁻¹]	Thorium concentration in the subsample .
²³⁰Th/²³²Th x10⁻⁶	Atomic ratio between isotopes of thorium, applied a factor of 10-6
[at/at]	
δ²³⁴U [med]	Relationship of activities between ²³⁴ U and ²³⁸ U, according to the following formula: $\delta^{234}\text{U} = ([^{234}\text{U}/^{238}\text{U}] - 1) \times 1000$
δ²³⁴U_{nit} [calc]	Value calculated according to the equation: $\delta^{234}\text{U}_{\text{init}} = \delta^{234}\text{U}_{\text{medida}} \times e^{\lambda(234)t}$ Being t the age ²³⁰ Th calculated and corrected
²³⁰Th/²³⁸U [act/act]	Isotopic ratio between ²³⁰ Th and ²³⁸ U in terms of activities.
²³⁰Th uncorr [y]	Calculated age, in years, according to Ivanovich & Harmon (1992), taking the year 1950 as a present reference.
²³⁰Th corr [y]	Corrected age, in years, and referenced to 1950, by assuming an initial isotopic ratio ²³⁰ Th/ ²³² Th (atomic) = 4.4±2.2x10-6, as the typical values of a material in secular equilibrium, and taking the

Decay constants: λ₂₃₈ = 1.55125x10⁻¹⁰; λ₂₃₄ = 2.82206x10⁻⁶; λ₂₃₀ = 9.1705x10⁻⁶

Table 5 Results of analysis by uranium series for the measured samples.

Sample	TOR 20 PR - 4000	TOR 20 PR - 4001	TOR 20 PR - 4002	TOR 20 PR - 4003	TOR 20 PR - 0001
Lab- Id	<i>SU-20205-3</i>	<i>SU-20205-4</i>	<i>SU- 20205-1</i>	<i>SU- 20205-2</i>	<i>SU- 20205-5</i>
SU-ID	SU477	SU478	SU475	SU476	SU479
²³⁸ U	81.8	73.9	63.4	72.0	36.9
[μg g ⁻¹]	(0.008)	(0.002)	(0.004)	(0.007)	(0.001)
²³² Th	34.9	107.4	91.5	109.0	1.3
[μg g ⁻¹]	(0.1)	(1.9)	(0.2)	(0.8)	(0.1)
²³⁰ Th/ ²³² Th x10 ⁻⁶	22.5	26.1	10.3	24.0	1309
[at/at]	(0.01)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(0.02)	(2)
δ ²³⁴ U	984.8	1249.8	496.4	1004.2	2181
[med]	(0.2)	(1.2)	(0.07)	(0.09)	(3)
δ ²³⁴ U _{init} [estimated]	1067.5 (0.2)	1955.9 (1.9)	563.6 (0.08)	1672.2 (0.15)	3367 (4)
²³⁰ Th/ ²³⁸ U	0.552	2.185	0.856	2.092	2.593
[act/act]	(0.008)	(0.002)	(0.004)	(0.007)	(0.0003)
²³⁰ Th	34569	210311	87296	264662	153925
[y]	(574)	(460)	(594)	(2772)	(1000)
²³⁰ Th corr	28604	158694	44983	180680	141406
[y]	(549)	(429)	(423)	(1513)	(369)

The values in parentheses indicate the uncertainties at level $\sigma = 1$ of the measurements in the same units as the result they accompany.

3. Analysis and interpretation of the results

The interpretation of the analytical results and translation into dating key has been carried out by applying the general radioactive decay equation and solving it using graphical methods. The agreement of the dates obtained graphically was checked by comparing them with those obtained using the Isoplot software. The decay constants and the results visualization scheme are those recommended by Prof. H. Cheng et al. (2013).

The results are compatible with the following minimum and maximum dating of the samples (table 6):

Table 6 Results of the dating of the samples received

Sample	TOR20PR 4000 <i>SU-20205-3</i>	- TOR20PR 4001 <i>SU-20205-4</i>	- TOR20PR 4002 <i>SU-20205-1</i>	- TOR20PR 4003 <i>SU-20205-2</i>	- TOR20PR 0001 <i>SU-20205-5</i>
Year	28 604	158 694	44 983	180 680	153 925
(1 σ)	(549)	(429)	(423)	(1 513)	(369)

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Topic 2: Taphonomic effects on bone remains in Middle Pleistocene sites

Work 3: Life history of archaeological remains: An investigation into the taphonomic effects of weathering and sedimentary pressure on two experimental models of archeo-paleontological assemblages simulating Middle Pleistocene sites.

Access offered : Experimental Archeology and Taphonomy Lab. Research Center on Human Evolution (CENIEH). Burgos, Spain.

Authors: Javier Llamazares, Felipe Cuartero, M^a Isabel Sarró, Mohamed Sahnouni, Nohemi Sala

1 Introduction

Experimental replication is a powerful tool in understanding taphonomic processes in order to determine whether geological or anthropogenic agencies were primarily responsible in the accumulation of fossil bones and stone tools in Paleolithic sites. Here we report a preliminary experimental study undertaken under highly controlled variables in the recently created Laboratory of Experimental Archeology and Taphonomy at the National Center for Research on Human Evolution (CENIEH) with the main goal of recognizing the effects of climatic, sedimentary, diagenetic and anthropogenic effects on the formation of two hypothetical models of archeo-paleontological assemblages within the context of Atapuerca sites.

Figure 16 Hypothesis “Glacier environments produce greater taphonomic effects on archaeo-paleontological assemblages than those referred to interglacial environments”

2 Material and methods

We reproduced two different hypothetical models of archeo-paleontological assemblages mimicking the sedimentary context of Atapuerca Middle Pleistocene sites. The first assemblage imitates the conditions of a glacial period and the second one an interglacial period. We used in each one of these experiments eight samples of replicated stone tools (2 in limestone, 2 in chert, 2 quartzite, 2 sandstone) and 8 bone fragments of 2 different animal taxa and size (cattle, lamb). We mixed the samples with sediments in metallic boxes in order to reproduce both contexts of glacial (50% limestone clasts, 50% clays) and interglacial (10% clasts, 90% clays) paleoenvironmental settings.

We simulated specific weathering conditions in the Dycometal CCK-25/2340MTe machine that is specifically built for this type of experiment (dry and cold vs wet and warm). Finally, we put those boxes of sediment under compression efforts in a compression Shimadzu AGS-100kNX simulator. The recognition of alterations, weathering effects and breakages types are recorded through high-resolution 3D models performed through a 3D light-reflected microscope (Olympus DSX1000 3D).

Figure 17 Specific weathering conditions: Dry and cold vs wet and warm

INDEPENDIENT VARIABLES	Glacial enviroment	Interglacial enviroment
Temperature	10 °C / -30 °C	40 °C / 20 °C
Humidity	30 %	70 %
Sediment	50% limestone clasts, 50% clays	10% clasts, 90% clays

Table 7 Specific weathering conditions: independents variables

18

19

20

Figure 18 Dycometal CCK-25/2340MTe **Figure 19** Shimadzu AGS-100Knx **Figure 20** Olympus DSX1000 3D
3 Results

A) Figure 21 BONES IN GALCIAL ENVIROMENT.

B) Figure 22 BONES IN INTERGLACIAL ENVIROMENT.

4 Conclusions and overview

Despite our first hypothesis was that glacial conditions were more destructive, several questions must be pointed out:

- In glacial environments, the stones (tools and clasts) are more altered, documenting etachments of parasitic flakes due to frost cycles, as well as a greater number of snap fractures due to sedimentary pressure in a matrix with a high volume of limestone clasts.
- Frost cycles helps to expand the incipient fissures in the bones fragments.
- Diagenetic fractures in bone fragments are common in our interglacial sample.
- Breakage in shrew mandibles, *Sorex* sp., (articular condyle mainly) is frequent in both environments, probably due to diagenetic factors.
- In the future it will be important to isolate the different variables to see how they affect individually to each sample under study.

5 References.

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- 4- Fischer, A., Vemming Jansen, P., Rasmussen, P. 1984. Macro and micro wear traces on lithic projectile points: experimental results and prehistoric examples. *Journal of Danish Archaeology* 3: 19-46.

Topic 3: Development of a procedure to evaluate the fragility and homogeneity of raw materials.

Work 4: Flintknapping and measuring: A protocol for evaluating quality in knappable raw materials through quantitative values of fragility and homogeneity.

Access offered : Geology/Geochronology Labs. Research Center on Human Evolution (CENIEH). Burgos, Spain.

Authors: Javier Llamazares, Felipe Cuartero, M^a Isabel Sarró, Jesus Mendez, carlos Saiz, Mohamed Sahnouni.

A protocol developed at CENIEH (Burgos, Spain) for the description under quantitative values of several features that affect to the quality of the raw materials used in flintknapping during Prehistoric times.

1. Introduction.

The quality of several rocks as obsidian, opal, flint, chert and quartzite are examined under flintknapping experiments and compared by devices as an Olympus DSX1000 3D digital microscope, a Leeb D scale durometer, and a Universal Testing Machine Shimadzu AGS-X 100 kN. The quality of the raw materials used in flintknapping is a major issue of knowledge that is usually difficult to quantify.

Nevertheless, certain physical properties such as fragility and homogeneity can be evaluated in several ways. We propose a method for evaluating raw materials' quality through two complementary analysis applying systematic knapping actions and measuring through several equipments that provide objective values.

2. Material and Methods.

16 different raw materials were analyzed in their hardness (durometer), roughness (3D microscope) and toughness (Universal Test Machine).

Figure 23 16 different raw materials

Obtaining slabs at Sixteen different raw materials compared thin section lab:

Figure 24 Obtaining thin sheets of samples

Figure 25 Sixteen different raw materials compared

Figure 27 Leeb D scale Durometer

Figure 26 Olympus DSX1000 3D digital microscope

Figure 28 Roughness

We compare these values with the length of the scars in a flintknapping action (pressure flaking with copper tip).

Figure 29 Universal Testing Machine Shimadzu AGS-X 100 kN

Figure 30 Flintknapping by pressure elasticity and endurance

3-Results.

Good correlation between the scale obtained at equipment measures and the mean length of scars at pressure flaking.

Nevertheless, some discordant values due to sampling faults or specific properties of some rocks.

Figures 31 Correlation between (average length in mm. extraction pressure) and (. UTM + Durometer + 3D Roughness)

Figures 32: Correlation between (average length in mm. extraction pressure) and (. UTM + Durometer + 3D Roughness)

4- Discussion and Conclusions

- Measures of displacement and deformation of the samples broken at the Universal testing machine seem good indications of elasticity and toughness/fragility in all the raw materials.
- Roughness can be easily and quickly recorded through the $S_v[\mu\text{m}]$ parameter in the Olympus DSX1000 3D digital microscope with significant values that correlate well to grain size and texture.
- Hardness can be easily measured repeatedly on samples cut in slab rectangular shapes with the Leeb D scale durometer as previously proposed by Corkum et al (2018).
- The flintknapping action here proposed (pressure flaking with a copper tip on 90° slabs) is suitable for evaluating the quality of many of the raw materials; nevertheless, some of them show differences that will be further compared with percussion flintknapping actions that seem more accurate for these rocks with coarse grain or less suitable petrography for pressure flaking.

5- References

Corkum, A. G., Asiri, Y., El Naggari, H., & Kinakin, D.(2018). The Leeb hardness test for rock: an updated methodology and UCS correlation. *Rock Mechanics and Rock Engineering*, 51(3), 665-675.

Topic 4: Procedure to minimize the effects derives of Micro CT or other X-Ray techniques in paleontological and paleoantreopological remains.

Work 5: Action protocol to minimize the degradation effects derived from the use of Micro CT in the study of paleontological heritage.

Access offered: Microcomputed tomography Lab. and Restauration/ conservation Lab. Research Center on Human Evolution (CENIEH). Burgos, Spain.

Author: Sofía de León, Raquel Lorenzo, Pilar Fernández

Introduction

Microcomputed tomography (MicroCT) is a variant of tomography computerized, diagnostic imaging technique that uses x-ray beams and electronic detectors that rotate around an object in a fixed position, generating images of their cross sections (Figures 16).

Presents a wide range of applications in various research areas, such as morphometric and biomechanical analyses, microanalysis of internal structures, generation of 3D models, etc. In the middle of the In the 70s it began to be used in the field of cultural heritage conservation, and In 1984 it was applied for the first time in the study of a fossil skull. [1]

Currently, MicroCT has replaced other destructive analysis methods such as taking samples, or taking sections and cuts in artifacts or ecofacts to study its interior. Although it uses a non-destructive technique, its application is not harmless to cultural property since it emits highly electromagnetic and ionizing radiation energy, and involves excessive manipulation of the object. Due to this, the use on Paleontological heritage must be protocolized to minimize risk.

Scanning is an exothermic process that causes an increase in temperature and a decrease in relative humidity in the MicroCT chamber.

In the team studio Phoenix v/tome/xs from GE® Measurement, present at the National Center for Research on Human Evolution (CENIEH), the Laboratory of Conservation and Restoration detected that the variation of these environmental parameters (maximum time oscillation), was related to the characteristics of the scan: position (size and density of the object, distance to the focus), current, power, filters and duration.

Figure 33- Placing a paleontological asset together with the support and platform inside the MicroCT scanning chamber

Figure 34- Placing a paleontological asset together with the support and platform inside the MicroCT scanning chamber.

These circumstances pose a potential risk for the conservation of paleontological assets given their sensitive hygroscopic and anisotropic nature, whose stress can generate degradation processes [2]. Furthermore, the technique requires the placement of the immobilized object in an axial position for the ideal range of the beam.

Which entails the participation of conservators-restorers in each heritage scan: encapsulation of the property in an expanded polystyrene structure (allowing the passage of X-rays); mounting with double-sided tape on a platform according to its size; placement inside the MicroCT; recording of the environmental parameters of both the camera and the Microtomography Laboratory; analysis of the previous and final state of the asset.

MicroCT is a very widespread diagnostic tool, necessary for the advancement of research in the field of human evolution, since it allows the non-destructive analysis of paleontological heritage of high scientific value and significance.

Thus, Its limited use is recommended, minimizing real and potential risks, as well as the design of specific preventive conservation strategies: a single scan, individual support, filter, minimum energy and current according to the characteristics of the property, among other. [3]

Figures 36 Characterization of Micro CT materials

Figure 37- Monitoring of the microenvironment inside the chamber of the MicroCT Phoenix /tome/xs of GE® s240 Measurement, during the scanning of a paleontological asset at the CENIEH.

References

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Topic 5: The use of Microtomography as a tool for paleontological and anthropological studies

Access offered : Microcomputed tomography (MicroCT)Labs. Research Center on Human Evolution (CENIEH). Burgos, Spain.

Authors: Eduardo Puértolas et al

General Concept:

The use of services provided by CENIEH, in this case the application of Computed Microtomography (microTAC) to fossil bones, has been carried out on several occasions. The main objective has been the scanning of Mesozoic vertebrates, mainly crocodiles, with the intention of seeing cavities and other internal structures that are normally hidden or inaccessible due to the rocky matrix that contains the fossil. The purpose of the data obtained from microTAC can be summarized as follows:

- **Internal anatomy of fossils:** CT scans allow paleontologists to visualize the internal structures of fossils without damaging them. This includes bones, teeth, soft tissues, and in some cases even preserved organs.
- **Three-dimensional reconstruction:** Precise 3D models of fossils can be created from images obtained with the CT scanner. This facilitates detailed study of morphology and allows analysis of functional and evolutionary aspects.
- **Taxonomic comparisons:** CT is a valuable tool that allows observation of anatomical characteristics that may be hidden from view, such as sutures, internal cavities, etc. Obtaining this information is very useful for classifying and comparing extinct species with other known ones. This helps to determine evolutionary relationships and understand past biological diversity.
- **Study of behavior:** By analyzing fossils in their three-dimensional context, scientists can infer aspects of the behavior and ecology of extinct organisms. In our case, TAC images and generated 3D models can be used for studies of paleoneuroanatomy. Paleoneuroanatomy is a branch of paleontology that focuses on the study of the brain structures and nervous system of extinct organisms through the analysis of fossils and endocranial molds. Its goal is to reconstruct and understand the cerebral anatomy of ancient species to obtain Detailed images of the interior of the skull and other tissues can be generated using microTAC scans. These images are generated in cross-sectional sections and then combined to create precise 3D models of the endocranial cavity. TAC images allow for the identification, mapping, or segmentation of internal impressions and features of the skull, which correspond to brain structures such as the brain, cerebral ventricles, olfactory bulbs, inner ear, and other parts of the nervous system. Precise measurements of the endocranial cavity can be made from this data and compared to modern species to infer aspects of the size and shape of the brain of fossil organisms. This allows inferences to be made about the cognitive, sensory, and behavioral abilities of fossil organisms. For example, cognitive, visual, olfactory, auditory abilities, etc. can be estimated. Therefore, comparing fossil

brains with those of modern species helps to understand the evolution of the nervous system and provides information about changes in behavior and cognition over time.

Work 6: A three-dimensional skeleton of Goniopholididae from the Late Jurassic of Portugal: implications for the Crocodylomorpha bracing system

1. Concept:

The paper focuses on the study of a three-dimensional skeleton of Goniopholididae from the Late Jurassic in Portugal, with implications for the understanding of crocodylomorphs. The main objective is to analyze the morphology and postcranial anatomy of this specimen to contribute to the understanding of the evolution and systematics of crocodylomorphs.

2. Case study-model system:

In this study we describe a partial articulated skeleton of a small neosuchian crocodylomorph from the Upper Jurassic of Portugal (Specimen specimen ML2555). The skeleton corresponds to the posterior region of the trunk and is composed of dorsal, ventral and limb osteoderms, dorsal vertebrae, thoracic ribs and part of the left hind limb. The study focused on the comparison of dermal armor (osteoderms) with that of several Jurassic, Cretaceous and present-day neosuchian crocodylomorphs, providing a detailed description of this type of osteoderms. The exceptional 3D preservation of the specimen and the use of a computerized microtomography at CENIEH allowed us to interpret the support system of this organism to evaluate whether previous models were accurate.

The support system is the set of vertebrae, osteoderms, ligaments and muscles that support the organism and are involved in its locomotion style. The characters observed in this specimen are congruent with Goniopholididae, a family of neosuchians abundant in most of the semi-aquatic ecosystems of the Jurassic and Cretaceous of Laurasia.

3. Protocol:

Specimen ML2555 was prepared mechanically with a pneumatic striker in the laboratories of the Museo da Lourinhã (where ML2555 is housed) and at the *Faculdade de Ciências e Tecnologia da Universidade Nova de Lisboa (Portugal)*. It is a process in which a tool driven by compressed air, known as a pneumatic or striker tool, is used to carefully remove the surrounding rock from the fossil. This method is commonly employed in paleontology to extract fossil specimens embedded in the rock matrix without damaging the more delicate structures. Paleontologists or fossil preparators use this tool to gradually remove the rock around the fossil, thus exposing fossil features and structures. This approach allows precise control over the preparation process and is especially useful when working with small or delicate fossils as was the case with ML2555.

It is essential to perform the preparation with extreme caution, as mishandling of the pneumatic stylus could result in irreparable damage to the fossil. Furthermore, in some cases, when the fossil is particularly fragile or the surrounding rock is too hard, it may be necessary to resort to alternative techniques, such as the use of more delicate hand tools or even three-dimensional scanning technologies to visualize hidden structures without touching the specimen.

For all these reasons, and due to the small size and fragility of ML2555, a complete preparation was not possible (Fig. 1A), so micro-CT scanning was performed to study the bones hidden by the rock matrix. The micro-CT was performed by V|Tome|X s 240 of GE Sensing & Inspections Technologies at the Centro Nacional de Investigación sobre Evolución Humana (CENIEH) (Burgos, Spain). Two separate scans were needed to cover the entire specimen as it came in several separate pieces. Limb bones generated 1800 images with a magnification of 5.33328759 and a voxel size of 0.03750032 mm; for the axial skeleton and osteoderms, we obtained 1800 images with a magnification of 4.65113026 and a voxel size of 0.04300030 mm. The raw data from each scan were imported, processed and segmented with 3D Slicer 4.9.0-2018 and ImageJ Fiji 1.52i. The obtained 3D models were visualized, analyzed, repositioned and rendered with MeshLab v.2016.12.

4. Limitations and advances of the protocol:

The use of compressed air strikers or punches in fossil preparation, known as "air scribe", is a common technique in paleontology, but it has some limitations and associated problems. Fossils are often very fragile and can be easily damaged by the use of percussion tools. This fragility limits the pressure and size of tools that can be used without causing damage. In addition, the precision in removing the rock matrix around the fossil may be limited, especially in delicate, detailed or difficult to access areas. Despite these limitations, preparation with compressed air strikers remains a valuable and effective technique when performed with care and experience. Preparators often combine several techniques to address these limitations and achieve the best possible results. As we have already discussed an alternative or complement to mechanical fossil preparation is the use of CT scanners to do such "preparation" virtually and thus not damage the fossil or save time, as mechanical preparation is much slower.

As for the use of CT in paleontological research, it presents significant challenges and advances. Limitations such as limited spatial resolution, difficulties with large fossils or densities similar to the surrounding rock, and possible image artifacts present obstacles to accurate data acquisition. However, technological advances in scanners and software have improved spatial resolution, scanning speed, and artifact reduction, allowing for more detailed and rapid capture of fossil anatomy.

5. Perspectives on future directions:

Several perspectives and future directions for research on this topic are envisioned from this work. First, it is crucial to continue exploring and discovering new specimens of Goniopholididae in the region, especially those that can provide additional information on their postcranial anatomy, ecology and evolution. In addition, more detailed analyses on the paleoecology of the area during that period are suggested, addressing aspects such as paleoenvironment, climate, vegetation and coexistence with other species. This would help to confirm or refute the locomotion style and amphibian lifestyle proposed for this family of neosuchian crocodylomorphs. The application of advanced technologies and methods in paleontological research, such as CT scanning and 3D modeling isotopic analyses and bone histology studies, is presented as a promising prospect for obtaining more detailed information on the anatomy, biomechanics and paleobiology of these fossil crocodylomorphs with no present-day representatives.

Figure 38 Fossil and 3D reconstruction of osteoderms and interpretation and comparison of the different support systems in Crocodylomorpha

6. Accesses Provided by the laboratory:

Scanning of the fossils was performed using the V|Tome|X s 240 micro-CT model from GE Sensing & Inspections Technologies at the Centro Nacional de Investigación sobre Evolución Humana (CENIEH) in Burgos, Spain. Two separate acquisitions were necessary to cover the entire specimen.

7. Conclusions:

In this work, a partial skeleton of a neosuchian crocodylomorph found in Portugal is described for the first time. Specimen ML2555 has characteristics that identify it as belonging to the family Goniopholididae. Through micro-CT scans, it could be confirmed that these crocodylomorphs had a closed paravertebral brace system and reduced epaxial musculature compared to other groups. Although the size of the specimen is small, it could not be determined whether it was a dwarf or juvenile individual due to pending histological analyses.

8. References:

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- Schwarz, D. (2002). A new species of *Goniopholis* from the Upper Jurassic of Portugal. *Palaeontology*, 45(1), 185-208

Work 7: First record of a giant bird (Ornithuromorpha) from the uppermost Maastrichtian of the southern Pyrenees, NE Spain

1. Concept:

In the evolutionary history of birds, giant forms have evolved in different periods and ecological contexts. In Europe, the first large birds, the Gargantuaviidae, appeared during the Late Cretaceous, and during the Paleogene more groups evolved into large forms. However, until now, no giant birds had been recorded during the terminal Maastrichtian in Europe, near the Cretaceous/Paleogene (K/Pg) boundary when the non-avian dinosaurs became extinct.

2. Case study-model system:

This study describes a cervical vertebra (MPZ 2019/264) from Beranuy (Huesca, NE Spain), which represents the first fossil evidence of a late Maastrichtian giant bird from Europe. The microtomography of the vertebra carried out at CENIEH allowed us to reconstruct its cavities, revealing a very large and intricate system of pneumatic cavities, being one of the characteristics that allowed us to assign it to Avialae. This finding demonstrates that large birds were part of the ecological communities of Iberia at the end of the Cretaceous, being present in the last hundreds of thousands of years before the K/Pg mass extinction event.

3. Protocol:

The vertebra fossil MPZ 2019/264 studied in this paper is housed in the Museum of Natural Sciences of the University of Zaragoza (Canudo, 2018). The specimen was embedded in a sandy carbonate matrix when collected in the field. Before being studied, the fossil was cleaned using physical and chemical methods (immersions in 10% dilute formic acid) to remove the surrounding rocky matrix. The protocol used to prepare fossils with acid will be explained in the following project.

A micro-CT scan was performed using a GE V|Tome|X scanner at CENIEH (Centro Nacional de Investigación sobre la Evolución Humana, Burgos, Spain). To examine the internal characteristics of the vertebra, the images obtained from the scanner were processed using Dragonfly software (Version 4.1, Object Research Systems).

To analyze the phylogenetic affinities of MPZ 2019/264, we included it in two phylogenetic analyses. A maximum parsimony phylogenetic analysis seeks to identify evolutionary relationships between fossils or present-day organisms using an approach that seeks the simplest and most direct explanation. It is based on finding an evolutionary tree that requires the least number of evolutionary changes (shared or different characters) to explain the differences observed between the species studied. This method assumes that the most plausible explanation is the one that minimizes the amount of evolutionary changes required, which helps to infer phylogenetic relationships among the analyzed organisms. Both datasets were edited using Mesquite V.3.31 and analyzed using TNT v.1.5. For the first Analysis, we used a character matrix including 1781 characters coded for 132 taxa, with representatives of the major pan-avian clades, to explore the avialan affinities of the specimen studied. Analysis 2 was conducted by including MPZ 2019/264 in the Mesozoic avian dataset and includes a total of 280 characters coded for 72 taxa. For both analyses, a heuristic tree search was performed, starting with 1000 Wagner tree replicates

followed by TBR branch swaps and maintaining 10 trees per replicate. This was followed with an additional round of tree bisection and reconnection (TBR), using trees in memory. Branch support was assessed with Bremer's decay index and 1000 replicates of standard bootstrap analysis.

Figure 39 Sections obtained from the microtomography reconstructing the cavities and pneumaticity of the vertebra studied. Below is the 3D reconstruction of the vertebra and the slices made

4. Limitations and advances of the protocol:

Since the limitations of mechanical and chemical preparation of fossils, as well as their CT scans, have already been explained in other sections of this report, we will focus this section on the cladistics section.

As already explained, cladistics by parsimony is a valuable tool in the reconstruction of phylogenetic relationships of extinct and extant organisms, but it has specific limitations when applied to fossils:

- Lack of complete data: Fossils are often incomplete, which can lead to gaps in information and difficulties in coding missing characters. This can distort the analysis by not having a complete picture of the anatomy of extinct species.
- Evolutionary convergence: Convergence, where different species develop similar but evolutionarily unrelated characteristics, can confound cladistic analysis if interpreted as evidence of close phylogenetic relationships. This type of problem related to evolutionary convergence has been evidenced in Crocodylomorpha, as phylogenies based on morphological characters may give different results from phylogenies based on DNA.

- Limitations in interpretation: Interpretation of character data can be subjective and researcher-dependent, which can lead to different results depending on who performs the analysis.

5. Perspectives on future directions:

To solve the above mentioned problems on the application of parsimony cladistic analysis in fossils there are several future perspectives and alternatives to this cladistic method.

- Inclusion of molecular data: The integration of molecular and morphological data can provide a more complete view of phylogenetic relationships. This is particularly valuable when working with fossils, as molecular information can fill gaps in the fossil record.

- Bayesian methods: Bayesian methods allow uncertainty to be incorporated into phylogenetic analysis, which helps to address gaps in the data and to consider variation in evolution more flexibly than parsimony.

- Complex evolutionary models: The development of more sophisticated models that consider specific evolutionary processes, such as variable rate of evolution and nonlinear evolution of characters, can improve the accuracy of phylogenetic reconstructions in fossils.

- Integration of multiple data and techniques: Combining morphological, molecular, paleoecological, and paleogeographic data together with more advanced analytical techniques can provide a more complete picture of phylogenetic relationships in the evolutionary context.

In summary, the integration of different types of data and the development of more advanced analytical methods are essential to improve the understanding of phylogenetic relationships in the fossil domain, overcoming some limitations associated with cladistics by parsimony.

6. Laboratory Offered Access:

The scan of the cervical vertebra MPZ 2019/264 was performed using the V|Tome|X s 240 micro-CT model from GE Sensing & Inspections Technologies at the Centro Nacional de Investigación sobre Evolución Humana (CENIEH) in Burgos, Spain.

7. Conclusions:

Vertebra MPZ 2019/264 was discovered at the 'Dolor' site in the southern Pyrenees (municipality of Beranuy, Huesca province, Spain) in Upper Maastrichtian deposits (66.3-66.052 million years ago). It represents the first evidence of a late Maastrichtian giant bird from the Ibero-Armorican Island. This vertebra belongs to a bird the size of a cassowary, and its most remarkable feature is the presence of a well-developed heterohelical joint combined with a high vascularity of the vertebral body observed thanks to CT. These features differentiate this taxon from other paravian theropods already recognized on the island. It is believed to belong to a new type of giant bird, although its exact relationship to other species is still uncertain due to the lack of complete fossils.

The cladistic analyses performed place MPZ 2019/264 within the Ornithuromorpha clade and are concordant with the comparisons. This discovery is the most modern evidence of a bird in Europe before the Cretaceous-Paleogene extinction, and suggests that these giant birds lived in the region

before this mass extinction 66 million years ago. New findings are expected to provide more information about this bird and its evolutionary history.

8. References:

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Work 8: New data on the neuroanatomy of basal eusuchian crocodylomorphs Allodaposuchidae) from the Upper Cretaceous of Spain.

1. Concept:

The main concept of the paper focuses on providing new data on the neuroanatomy of basal eusuchian crocodylomorphs (Allodaposuchidae) from the Late Cretaceous of Spain.

2. Case study-model system:

The Pyrenees (northeastern Spain) has provided a rich and diverse collection of Upper Cretaceous vertebrate fossil remains, most notably the Crocodylomorpha. This record includes remains of the last representatives of the crocodiles of the family Allodaposuchidae, to which the species of the Aragonese record *Arenysuchus gascabadiolorum* and *Agaresuchus subjuniperus* belong. This clade is related to the present-day crocodylians and disappeared at the same time as the non-avian dinosaurs during the Cretaceous-Paleogene (K/Pg) extinction event. In this context, the holotype skull of *Arenysuchus gascabadiolorum* underwent a microtomography scan at CENIEH facilities to obtain the three-dimensional reconstruction of its internal cranial cavities, including the brain, nerves, blood vessels, paratympanic sinus system and paranasal sinuses. These specimens offer a unique window to understand the neurocranial structure of these prehistoric animals.

3. Protocol:

The protocol used involves detailed analyses of neurocranial structure, including techniques such as laboratory preparation of fossils, 3D reconstructions, computed tomography (CT scans), and comparisons with other related groups of modern and fossil animals.

The preparation of these two fossils in the laboratory involved additional techniques to that already discussed in previous work on mechanical preparation with compressed air strikers. For the *Arenysuchus* skull, this technique was combined with the use of acid baths. The use of acid in the preparation of vertebrate fossils is a common technique in paleontology to remove the surrounding rock and reveal the fossil within it. This is done by immersing the fossil in an acid solution, usually acetic, formic, or dilute hydrochloric acid. Before immersing the fossil in acid, a few preliminary steps can be performed. This includes removing excess sediment or loose rock around the fossil to expose it. The fossil is then carefully placed in a dilute acid solution. The type and concentration of acid is selected based on the type of rock surrounding the fossil and the type of fossil itself. The acid dissolves the surrounding rock without (ideally) damaging the structure of the fossil.

To protect the fossil regions exposed to acid, these parts are protected with consolidant (paraloid B72). The duration of immersion varies according to the composition of the rock and the strength of the fossil. It is crucial to continuously monitor the process to avoid damaging the fossil. Most fossils require multiple immersions in acid with different concentrations for effective cleaning. Once the rock has been removed, the fossil is meticulously washed to remove any acid residue. In addition, the fossil can be neutralized by immersing it in an alkaline solution to prevent continued

corrosion due to the residual presence of acid. Paleontologists often combine this technique with others, such as the use of delicate hand tools or mechanical cleaning methods, to obtain the best results without damaging the specimen.

For the preparation of the *Agaresuchus* skull, compressed air striker preparation and the use of sandblasting were combined. Sandblasting is a fossil preparation technique that involves the use of a jet of abrasive particles (usually fine quartz calcium carbonate sand or other abrasive media such as metal shavings) directed at high pressure towards the fossil. This is done using a specialized machine that projects the particles at high velocity.

At the University of Zaragoza, this work is carried out inside an isolated box containing the sandblasting control and the fossil, which are manipulated with protective gloves through two holes.

As for the protocol used for the CT, it is basically the same used in the other projects already mentioned. Due to the difference in size between the skulls of *Arenysuchus gascabadiolorum* and *Agaresuchus subjuniperus*, these had to be scanned with different equipment and voltage and current settings, which generated images with different resolutions and pixel sizes. *Arenysuchus* MPZ 2011/184 scanned on the micro-TAC (V|Tome|X s 240 of GE Sensing & Inspections Technologies) at the Centro Nacional de Investigación sobre la Evolución Humana (CENIEH, Burgos, Spain), with a voltage of 170 kV and a current intensity of 300 mA. The scan resulted in 3096 images with 0.06600049 mm voxel size and an image resolution of 2024 x 2024 pixels. Due to a larger size and not fitting in the above machine, the skull of *Agaresuchus* MPZ 2012/288 was scanned with an industrial CT scanner (Yxlon Y.TU 225-D03 bifocal tube model and PerkinElmer XRD 1622 detector) at the University of Burgos (Burgos, Spain), with a voltage of 225 kV and a current intensity of 1.5 mA.

The resulting scan produced 2720 images with a voxel size of 0.143 mm and an image resolution of 2048 x 2048 pixels. The data from each scan were processed and segmented with Dragonfly v. 2020.2 software to obtain 3D models, which were visualized, analyzed and rendered with Blender v. 2.90.1. Subsequently, these 3D reconstructions were used for linear and volumetric measurements of the internal cranial cavities.

4. Limitations and advances of the protocol:

The use of acid in fossil preparation can be effective in removing surrounding rock and revealing bone or mineralized structure. However, there are several important limitations and considerations:

- Damage to the fossil: Acid can damage the structure of the fossil if not used carefully. It can erode or corrode the surface of the fossil, erasing fine details or damaging delicate parts. Several regions of the *Arenysuchus* skull were affected by this process.
- Difficulty in controlling the reaction: Acid can react unpredictably with different types of minerals. Some fossils may contain minerals that react violently with certain types of acids, which can irreparably damage the fossil.

- Toxicity: Many types of acids are dangerous and toxic to work with without proper protective equipment. This poses a health risk to the preparer and requires careful and safe handling.
- Time and cost: Acid preparation can be a slow and costly process. Careful monitoring and multiple rinses are required to completely remove the acid from the sample.

Sandblasting is an effective technique for fossil preparation, but it can be risky if not used carefully, as it can damage the structure of the specimen by puncturing or marking it. For this reason, it is common for paleontologists to combine several preparation techniques to obtain the best results without compromising the integrity of the fossil.

As for the use of CT, this also has a number of limitations to take into account:

- Resolution: CT resolution may be limited in some cases. For very small fossils or detailed structures, the resolution may not be sufficient to capture all anatomical details.
- Limitations of fossil size: Very large fossils may not fit within the available CT scanners, making it difficult to obtain a complete image without performing scans in sections that must then be digitally assembled. As mentioned above, the skull of *Agaresuchus*, due to its size, could not be scanned on the V|Tome|X microCT at CENIEH, so it had to be scanned on a lower resolution CT scanner at the University of Burgos.
- Data interpretation: Interpreting CT data can be complicated, especially if complex fossils are involved. It requires specific expertise and knowledge in anatomy to reconstruct the fossil.
- Time-consuming: The process of fossil segmentation, that is, painting and delimiting the different parts of the fossil in the 2D images, to join them and make a 3D reconstruction, is a very time-consuming process. Generally distinguishing the rocky matrix from the fossil is usually difficult since both materials usually present a similar density, that is why this segmentation must be done almost manually, a process that can take from weeks to months of work.

5. Perspectives on future directions:

The use of computed tomography (CT) to reconstruct the endocranium of fossils has been evolving and further progress is projected in several directions:

- Improved resolution: Advances in scanning technology will allow for greater spatial resolution, which means an ability to capture finer details of internal structures. This will be crucial for accurate endocranial reconstruction and identification of smaller anatomical features.
- Advanced visualization techniques: It is expected that visualization techniques will be developed and improved to analyze CT data in a more detailed and comprehensive manner. This will include more accurate segmentation tools to differentiate soft tissue, rock matrix and bone, and more accurate three-dimensional reconstruction of endocranial structures.
- Functional analysis: The ability to infer physiological and behavioral functions from endocranial morphology is expected to advance. This could include the reconstruction of brain areas related to senses, behavior and specific adaptations.

- Biomechanical modeling: The use of CT to reconstruct endocraniums could also be integrated into biomechanical models to better understand how these cranial structures might have influenced behavior, locomotion, and sensory function in fossil organisms. In summary, future prospects for the use of CT for fossil endocranium reconstruction are geared toward greater accuracy, integration with other technologies, and a deeper understanding of the function and evolution of these anatomical structures.

Figure 40 Photos of the original fossil

Figure 41 Three-dimensional reconstruction of the skull (with transparency) and cranial cavities of the holotype of *Arenysuchus gascabadiolorum*

6. Access Offered by the laboratory:

The *Arenysuchus* scan was performed using the V|Tome|X s 240 micro-CT model from GE Sensing & Inspections Technologies at the Centro Nacional de Investigación sobre Evolución Humana (CENIEH) in Burgos, Spain. The *Agaresuchus* scan was performed on an industrial CT

scanner (Yxlon Y.TU 225-D03 bifocal tube model and PerkinElmer XRD 1622 detector) at the University of Burgos (Burgos, Spain).

7. Conclusions:

The 3D reconstruction of the cranial cavities of these two Pyrenean species were compared with those of other crocodylomorphs and it was observed that the endocranial anatomy is consistent with their phylogenetic position within Allodaposuchidae and showing similar morphologies and neurosensory and cognitive abilities to those present in other allodaposuchids. Its inferred sensory abilities, such as a keen sense of smell and relatively good vision, are within the range observed in most eusuchids and Crocodylia, suggesting that the sensory and cognitive abilities observed in late Mesozoic crocodylians were already similar to those observed in present-day crocodylians.

8. References:

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Work 9: Neuroanatomy of the crocodylomorph *Portugalosuchus azenhae* from the late cretaceous of Portugal

1. Concept:

This study presents the first detailed description of the neurocranial anatomy and a neuroanatomical analysis of *Portugalosuchus azenhae*, an eusuchian crocodylomorph from the Late Cretaceous of Portugal. Although originally classified as a possible Crocodylia and one of the oldest representatives of this clade, its phylogenetic position remains controversial.

2. Case study-model system:

Using high-resolution microtomography imaging, this study aimed to improve the original description of the taxon and update the scarce neuroanatomical knowledge of Eusuchia and Crocodylia from this time interval, crucial for understanding the origin and evolution of these clades. The three-dimensional models resulting from the CT data allowed a detailed description of the well-preserved neurocranium and internal cavities. This made possible the reconstruction of the cavities of the olfactory region, nasopharyngeal ducts, brain, nerves, carotid arteries, blood vessels, paratympanic sinus system and inner ear, which allowed estimating some neurosensory capacities.

3. Protocol:

The study focuses on the skull and mandible of *Portugalosuchus azenhae*, holotype ML1818, housed at the Museu da Lourinhã (Lourinhã, Portugal). The specimen was almost completely prepared using a pneumatic hammer and consolidated with Paraloid B-72 prior to image acquisition. Three-dimensional reconstructions of the skull and mandible were performed by computed tomography (CT scan) on the micro-CT V|Tome|X s 240 of GE Sensing & Inspections Technologies at the Centro Nacional de Investigación sobre Evolución Humana (CENIEH) (Burgos, Spain). The scans generated 1599 images (3048 for the mandible) with a voxel size of 0.11000033 mm (0.05649985 for the mandible) and image resolution of 2024 × 2024 pixels. The raw scan data were processed and segmented with Avizo Software 2020.3 (Thermo Fisher Scientific) and the resulting 3D models were rendered with Blender v. 2.90.1 (Blender Foundation).

The description of the fossil was also re-expanded and new hidden characters could be encoded thanks to the images provided by the microTAC. With these new data, a new phylogenetic analysis was performed based on the Rio and Mannion (2021) matrix including 330 characters and 144 taxa. The analysis was performed using the New Technology Search in TNT v 1.5 (July 2022 version).

4. Limitations and advances of the protocol:

Since most of the analyses performed in these papers agree, we will not elaborate on their limitations again, so we will focus on the more specific issues of this paper. The results obtained

here and in the analysis by Rio and Mannion (2021) contrast slightly with other recent analyses that combine the use of DNA and morphological characters (Darlim et al., 2022; Lee & Yates, 2018). These aforementioned works place "Thoracosauridae" and *Portugalosuchus* (along with other taxa such as *Borealosuchus* spp. and *Planiocraniidae*) outside of Crocodylia as successive eusuchian taxa of the crown group. This problem is probably due to the presence in the matrix of convergent characters with little phylogenetic significance in some taxa such as the longirrostrines, due to adaptations of their snouts to more aquatic life forms. The identification of convergences and the elimination of such problematic characters from the phylogenetic matrices will help to improve the topologies obtained in cladistics based on morphology and fossils.

Figure 42 Original fossil and 3D models of the reconstruction of the bones and internal cavities of *Portugalosuchus azenhae*.

5. Perspectives on future directions:

As a future exercise, it would be interesting to replicate these analyses by including the new data obtained here, along with DNA data, and using other cladistic approaches such as Bayesian analyses. In addition, recovering more phylogenetically related fossils of similar ages could shed light on this issue.

6. Accesses Provided by the laboratory:

The *Portugalosuchus* scan was performed using the V|Tome|X s 240 micro-CT model from GE Sensing & Inspections Technologies at the Centro Nacional de Investigación sobre Evolución Humana (CENIEH) in Burgos, Spain.

7. Conclusions:

In this study, the results of the first detailed anatomical description of the neurocranium and the neuroanatomical analysis of the holotype of the Portuguese Cenomanian eusuchian crocodylomorph *Portugalosuchus azenhae* (ML1818) are presented. The resulting 3D model has allowed a detailed description of the neurocranium, correcting and complementing previous observations. The anatomy of the olfactory region, nasopharyngeal ducts, brain, nerves, carotid arteries, blood vessels, paratympanic sinuses and inner ear has been reconstructed. The reconstruction of these internal cavities has also made it possible to estimate their neurosensory capacities. Compared to other crocodylians, these analyses demonstrated that *Portugalosuchus*, as early as the Cretaceous, possessed olfactory acuity, vision, hearing and cognitive abilities within the range observed in other extinct eusuchians and present-day crocodylians. In addition, new anatomical data provided by the CT scan were included in a phylogenetic analysis. The position of *Portugalosuchus* differs slightly from the original publication, placing it now a Gavialoidea, within the clade Crocodylia. This position contrasts with other recent analyses that include DNA information and place *Portugalosuchus* outside of Crocodylia (Darlim et al., 2022).

To adequately test these phylogenies, future cladistic analyses should consider the new morphological features observed in *Portugalosuchus* by coding them together with DNA data.

8. References:

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Work 10: How accurate are medical CT and micro-CT techniques compared to classical histology when addressing the growth of the internal rib parameters.

Access offered : Microcomputed tomography (MicroCT 9Labs. Research Center on Human Evolution (CENIEH). Burgos, Spain.

Authors: Daniel García, Pedro R. Moya et al.

1. Introduction

The study of the rib internal anatomy and its cross-sectional morphology has attracted the interest of the biological anthropology community for decades. This is because:

- 1) Ribs are more frequently uncorrected proof accessible for destructive techniques, which have been traditionally necessary to study the rib internal anatomy.
- 2) Ribs are potentially less subjected to the support of the weight of the body, which alters the bone micro-anatomy throughout secondary remodeling, being less -mental factors.
- 3) Ribs can provide important information about breathing biomechanics and other factors such as phylogeny or ontogeny.

In addition, the internal anatomy because of the potential importance for the estimation of the sex or the age-at-death of the individual, but this process was typically destructive and can be ethically reprovable depending on the case, such as in the case of valuable or unique fossil specimens (Importantly, there is a growing interest in avoiding destructive methods to study the internal anatomy of the bones, and recent research is showing that X-ray-based techniques such as medical or micro-CT scanning can provide some important information about the internal properties of the ribs with a minimum invasion of the bone). With these techniques, previous research has focused on the quantitative properties of the ribs, measuring variables such as thickness, porosity, % of the mineral area in the cross-section, connectivity, etc.. It is true that these X-ray-based methods, even though produce a huge amount of information about mechanical aspects of the ribs, do not have enough resolution to allow measure histomorphometric parameters as osteons number and/or type, parameters that are necessary to get the detail to estimate sex or age of the individual. Despite these limitations, CT-based methods produce also important information about biomechanical, developmental, or even phylogenetic trends in the costal skeleton and the thorax. For example, Holcombe et al. (2019) used medical-CT-scanning on central ribs to study the bone thickness and cross-sectional geometry, inferring general sexually dimorphic trends on the central ribs, which could be in line with research on the functional morphology of the ribcage.

Beresheim et al. (2019) used micro-CT scanning to quantify optical area, cortical thickness, the major and minor diameters of the rib, the trabecular thickness, and trabecular separation increase with age. Finally, López-Rey Pérez et al. (2022) used micro-CT techniques in a phylogenetic framework to

address the internal anatomy of ribs from humans, chimpanzees, and *Australopithecus africanus* Sts-14 to infer potential evolutionary or locomotor convergencies in the costal skeleton between human ancestors and great apes. Latimer et al. (2016) also used micro-CT to analyze the internal structure of the ribs of KSD-VP 1/1, hypothesizing that the internal anatomy of the rib in *A. afarensis* from Woranso-Mille (Latimer et al. 2016) had a similar rib morphology compared to modern humans.

All this research points out the huge importance of X-ray-based (non-destructive) methods to infer important aspects of ontogeny, sexual dimorphism, comparative anatomy, or even phylogeny of the ribcage. However, as it can be noted above, previous research has used a variety of ent microns accuracies for the micro-CT. We do not know if methods (medical or micro-CT) compared to classical histological techniques. In addition, recent research has observed that some cortical parameters are underestimated by micro-CT compared to classical histological techniques, but it has been tested only in the tibia of human adults (Schmidutz et al. 2021).

Last but not least, important changes have been reported in the ontogeny of human ribs using classical histological methods, with the relative amount of mineral content of the rib decreasing throughout the ontogeny (García-Martínez et al. 2017). This has been also supported by research using micro-CT methods (Beresheim et al. 2020), but since Schmidutz et al. (2021) has proposed caution when comparing classical histology with micro-CT methods, especially in very early ontogenetic stages where the size of the rib can represent a challenge for the resolution of the micro-CT.

Aims of this study mineral content of the rib (% Min. Ar.) in the cross-section combining classical histological techniques, medical-CT, -by mineralized tissue including the trabecular bone, as an uncorrected proof Ar. as a reference, we aim to quantify if medical and micro-CT under or over-estimate the information obtained from the histology during the ontogeny. Also, we aim to quantify the if medical-CT under- or over-estimates the % of the mineral Material and methods Fourteen left 1st ribs were carefully selected from the osteoarchaeological collection of the Santa María de la Soledad First ribs were selected because their sequential position is much easier to assess in the archaeological and the fossil record, and because their more robust morphology makes them better preserved also in the record .

From the whole sample of ribs, we only selected 1st ribs that showed no taphonomical or pathological alterations that could alter -netic spectra. The archaeological collection contains more than 200 skeletons and has been described as an ossuary, dating from the 12th to 18th centuries. Due to their exceptional stage of preservation, the samples have been used for previous histological studies and results have been published elsewhere. For this study, we have selected exceedingly well-preserved ribs to avoid possible diagenetic alterations that could frustrate their microanatomical description. Information about the age-atfrom the individuals studied here was estimated in García-Martínez et al. (2017) using a 3D geometrics morphometrics approach, and the information can be observed in Table 8.

Histological methods

Thin sections of the selected ribs were obtained from the previous studies), we manually trimmed a 1 cm block from each rib and submerged it in transparent resin (EpoFix resin mixed with EpoFix Hardener). Bubbles were extracted using a vacuum pump and, from each rib block, we prepared a observation using transmission microscopy (CX31 polarized light microscope equipped with a DP70 camera both from Olympus, Hamburg, Germany).

To select the exact area for trimming (midshaft of the rib) and homologize this area in the complete 1st sample for trimming, we measured the tubercle-ventral arch (TVA). This measurement has been

curvature of the rib from the lateral end of the articular surface of the tubercle to the sternal end of the rib” (and selected the middle of it as the area for trimming (midshaft of the rib). After photographing the total area of the midshaft cross-sections using an x4-tomontage using Geographical Information Systems (GIS)software (ArcGIS 9.3, Esri, Redlands, California, USA) as previously described.

Using histology-tomical structures over the microscope photomontages), we drew a total of 3995 polygons (the number of polygons differs for each individual) to describe the rib cross-sections.

X-ray based techniques (medical and micro-CT scanning).

The polished blocks to which the thin sections of the selected ribs that were measured with classical histological techniques, were medical-CT scanned and micro-CT scanned at slice of the polished blocks, being the immediately following cross-section to the one of the thin sections, also representing the rib midshaft. The thin sections that were analyzed using histological techniques could not be scanned because the resolution of the medical-CT was not enough to capture the thickness of the thin sections.

Id	Cross-sectional area (mm²)	Age group (G1–G5)
R1(AL_c01)	3.88	Perinatal (G1)
R2(AL_c05)	7.71	Perinatal-Infant (G1)
R3(AL_c02)	7.84	Perinatal-Infant (G1)
R4(AL_c16)	11.29	Infant (G2)
R5(AL_c15)	9.93	Infant (G2)
R6(AL_c14)	11.47	Infant (G2)
R7(AL_c13)	17.00	Infant-Child (G3)
R8(AL_c10)	71.00	Juvenile-Adolescent (G3)
R9(AL_c07)	57.52	Adolescent (G4)
R10(AL_c06)	63.50	Adolescent (G4)
R11(AL_c09)	63.82	Adolescent (G4)
R12(AL_c12)	49.53	Adult (G5)
R13(AL_c08)	55.08	Adult (G5)
R14(AL_c11)	68.77	Adult (G5)

Table 8 Basic information of the specimens studied here, showing Id, cross-sectional area, and age group from this study.

The medical-CT scans were performed at the Radiology Service of University Hospital La Paz (Madrid, Spain) with a 16-MDCT scanner (Somatom Sensation 16, Siemens Medical Solutions, Erlangen, Germany). The scanning voltage was 120 kV, the current was 160 mA and all imaging was performed with a resolution of 0.66 mm, table feed of 30 mm per rotation, and rotation time of 0.6 seconds per 360°. We use this resolution since it is the standard resolution when carrying out thoracic medical-CT-scanning (Gralla et al. 2005). The micro-CT scanning of the thin sections was scanned at the micro-CT laboratory of the CENIEH using a V|Tome|X s 240 equipment (GE Sensing & Inspections Technologies). The scanning voltage was 140 kV, the current was 150 μ A and all imaging was performed with a resolution of 1) 0.09 mm (90 microns) and rotation time of 3 seconds per (9–17 microns) and rotation time of 3 seconds per 360°, the quality used for previous works employing micro-CT methods for the study of human ribs (López-Rey Pérez et al. 2021; López-Rey Pérez et al. 2022) and the HD quality represents the maximum accuracy allowed by the limitation of distance (FOD) was 940.95 microns for both HD and SD micro-CT qualities, but the focal detector distance (FDD) for the HD and SD was 42.35 and 423.43 microns, respectively.

The selected DICOM images were exported and subsequently analyzed.

Quantification of the %.

Min. Ar. Cross-sectional images exported from histology, medical, and micro-CT were imported in Fiji software (Schindelin et al. 2012) was calculated as $[(A_{\text{total}} - A_{\text{amneral}})/A_{\text{total}}] * 100$. It is as the area occupied by mineralized tissues, including the trabecular bone, and has been successfully tested and applied in previous research (Cambra-Moo et al. 2014; Cambra-Moo et al. 2015; García Gil et al. 2016; García-Martínez et al. 2017; López-Rey Pérez et al. 2021; López-Rey Pérez et al. 2022). This process was carried out using a semi-automatic threshold-based method (Schindelin et al. 2012), and the brightness/contrast was 522/631 for the medical-CT DICOM images, 10390/26605 for the SD micro-CT DICOM images, and 5300/11300-12100/31400 for the SD micro-CT DICOM images. Threshold was 60 for all the measurements carried out.

Statistical analyses for inter-technique comparison

The % Min. Ar. values are descriptively reported for all the individuals and methods, and basic statistics such as the number of specimens, mean and standard deviation are also a Student's t-test or Mann-Whitney test to statistically test - techniques, depending on the normality of the sample, which was tested using a Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test. We also explored the variation in the % Min. Ar. Between groups and did not carry out statistical tests.

	Histology	Medical-CT	Micro-CT (SD)	Micro-CT (HD)	Area (mm)	Age Group
R1	90.46	100.00	92.28	93.30	3.88	G1
R2	61.09	100.00	83.43	63.68	7.71	G1
R3	78.83	100.00	83.44	76.50	7.84	G1
R4	66.34	100.00	83.20	67.25	11.29	G2
R5	71.5	100.00	81.00	67.30	9.93	G2
R6	80.99	100.00	84.80	83.97	11.47	G2
R7	79.28	100.00	79.00	79.90	17.00	G3
R8	71.78	96.47	76.00	74.76	71.00	G3
R9	55.86	75.00	67.26	54.06	57.52	G4
R10	68.36	81.95	76.37	69.00	63.5	G4
R11	50.5	87.86	64.50	56.08	63.82	G4
R12	39.45	75.87	65.1	50.6	49.53	G5
R13	56.41	83.25	70.30	41.46	55.08	G5
R14	59.71	76.83	67.60	55.92	68.77	G5

Table 9 Id and % Min. Ar. values measured following the three techniques compared in this study.

Results

The % Min. Ar. calculated for each of the specimens and the different techniques are show in Table 2. Our results show non-mineral areas, but its resolution provides larger values of % Min. Ar. Compared to the histological techniques, these differences are only slightly larger. When we analyzed the statistical significance of that difference we observe that the HD and the SD micro CT provides 0.23 and 10.27 larger % Min. Ar. compared to histology, respectively ($p = 0.98$; Table 3). Importantly, the difference between histology and HD micro CT was not statistically significant, whereas the difference between histology and SD micro –CT was statistically significant ($p = 0.03$; Table 10).

Regarding the comparison between histology and medical-CT methods, ther first important resul to highlight is that the resolution of a standard medical-CT (0.66 mm.) is not enough to differentiate non-mineral areas of the rib cross-sections up to juvenile/adolescent specimens (Table 2), because we were unable to differentiate any non –mneral space in the rib cross-sections of young specimens (Fig. 1). From this age group onwards, that resolution is enough to differentiate between mineral and non-mineral spaces (Table 10), but it provides much larger results of % Min. Ar. (24.76 larger) compared to histological techniques, which was statistically significant ($p < 0.01$; Table 10).

Histology vs. μ -CT (HD)		μ -CT (HD) vs. μ -CT (SD)	
Histology	μ -CT (HD)	μ -CT (HD)	μ -CT (SD)
Mean: 66.47	Mean: 66.7	Mean: 66.70	Mean: 76.73
s.d.: 13.68	s.d.: 14.25	s.d.: 14.25	s.d.: 13.68
t: 0.04; p: 0.97		t: 2.25; p: 0.03	
Difference between means: 0.23		Difference between means: 10.04	
Kolmogorov-Smirnov p-value: 0.98		Kolmogorov-Smirnov p-value: 0.11	
Histology vs. μ -CT (SD)		μ -CT (HD) vs. medical-CT	
Histology	μ -CT (HD)	μ -CT (HD)	μ -CT (SD)
Mean: 66.47	Mean: 76.73	Mean: 66.70	Mean: 91.23
s.d.: 13.68	s.d.: 8.61	s.d.: 14.25	s.d.: 10.50
t: 2.38; p: 0.03		U: 16; z: 3.77; p < 0.01	
Difference between means: 10.27		Difference between means: 24.53	
Kolmogorov-Smirnov p-value: 0.11		Kolmogorov-Smirnov p-value: < 0.01	
Histology vs. medical-CT		μ -CT (SD) vs. medical-CT	
Histology	medical-CT	μ -CT (SD)	medical-CT
Mean: 66.47	Mean: 91.23	Mean: 76.73	Mean: 91.23
s.d.: 13.68	s.d.: 10.50	s.d.: 13.68	s.d.: 10.50
U: 15; z: 3.82; p < 0.01		U: 35; z: 2.84; p < 0.01	
Difference between means: 24.76		Difference between means: 14.50	
Kolmogorov-Smirnov p-value: < 0.01		Kolmogorov-Smirnov p-value: 0.01	

Table 10 Basic statistics of the different techniques for the quantification of the % Min. Ar., showing the mean and the standard deviation for each technique

Comparing the two micro-CT qualities, our results show that the SD provides larger values of 10.04 on average compared to the HD micro-CT, which was statistically significant ($p < 0.01$; [Table 10](#)). Comparing the micro-CT with the medical-CT, the medical-CT provides larger values than the micro-CT. On average, medical-CT provides larger values of 24.53 and 14.50 compared to the HD and SD micro-CT, both of them being statistically significant (comparing differences by age group, we observe in the averages the same differences that we observe in the case before, but we specify that the inter-technique differences in adults are larger than in younger individuals ([Table 11](#))).

Figure 43: comprehensive image showing several first ribs from different ontogenetic stages ranging from perinate to adult where it is possible to observe the different resolution given by the histology, HD and SD micro-CT, and medical-CT. All of the images are in real scale except the perinate and the infant that has been magnified by x2 and x1.5, respectively.

	Age group	Area (mm ²)	Histology vs. μ -CT (HD)	Histology vs. μ -CT (SD)	Histology vs. med. CT	μ -CT (HD) vs. μ -CT (SD)	μ -CT (HD) vs. med. CT	μ -CT (SD) vs. med. CT
R1	G1	3.88	-3.14	-2.01	-10.55	1.09	-6.70	7.72
R2	G1	7.71	-4.24	-36.57	-63.69	-31.01	-36.32	16.57
R3	G1	7.84	2.96	-5.85	-26.86	-9.07	-23.50	16.56
Mean	G1	6.48	-1.47	-14.81	-33.70	-8.56	-22.17	13.62
R4	G2	11.29	-1.37	-25.41	-50.74	-23.72	-32.75	16.80
R5	G2	9.93	5.87	-13.29	-39.86	-20.36	-32.70	19.00
R6	G2	11.47	-3.68	-4.70	-23.47	-0.99	-16.03	15.20
Mean	G3	10.90	0.27	-14.47	-38.02	-10.16	-27.16	17.00
R7	G3	17.00	-0.78	0.35	-26.14	1.13	-20.10	21.00
R8	G3	71.00	-4.15	-5.88	-34.40	-1.66	-21.71	21.22
Mean	G3	44.00	-2.47	-2.76	-30.27	-0.17	-20.91	21.11
R9	G4	57.52	3.22	-20.41	-34.26	-24.42	-20.94	10.32
R10	G4	63.5	-0.94	-11.72	-19.88	-10.68	-12.95	6.81
R11	G4	63.82	-11.05	-27.72	-73.98	-15.01	-31.78	26.59
Mean	G4	61.61	-2.92	-19.95	-42.71	-9.66	-21.89	14.57
R12	G5	54.08	-28.26	-65.02	-92.32	-28.66	-25.27	14.20
R13	G5	55.08	26.50	-24.62	-47.58	-69.56	-41.79	15.56
R14	G5	68.77	6.35	-13.21	-28.67	-20.89	-20.91	12.01
Mean	G5	59.31	1.53	-34.29	-56.19	-18.34	-29.32	13.92

Table 11 Difference I the % Mi. Ar each age group using the three differents tecniques. The average by age group is shown but because of the limited number of specimens in each group, no further statistics were carried out. Legend: μ -CT = micro computed- tomography; med-CT = medical computed-tomography.

Discussion and conclusions

Recent research in the study of the internal anatomy of the rib, aiming to quantify parameters such as the thickness, porosity, or connectivity is trying to avoid classical destructive histological techniques, proposing that some variables can be analyzed using X-ray-based methods such as medical or micro-CT (Holcombe et al. 2019; Beresheim et al. 2020). Destructive techniques are usually avoided to analyze the archeological record but this issue becomes a huge challenge facing the fossil record when the uniqueness of the specimens is more apparent. Also, X-ray-based methods take a considerably smaller amount of time compared to classical histological techniques, which could be considered a great advantage for the scientific community.

Among these methods, it is important to highlight the use of medical- and micro-CT techniques

to study the internal anatomy of the bones (Gielkens et al. 2008; Smilg 2017). On the one hand, micro-CTs have a larger resolution and accuracy compared to the medical-CT (Hashimoto et al. 2006; Gielkens et al. 2008; Artachevarria et al. 2011; Van Dessel et al. 2013), but they are not widely used because:

- 1) CT-based techniques are usually expensive and difficult to afford by research projects with small funding sources, but indeed, collaborations between public hospitals and research institutions (Bastir et al. 2013; García-Martínez et al. 2014; Bastir et al. 2017a; Bastir et al. 2017b; García-Martínez et al. 2018; García-Martínez et al. 2019) are making the use of medical CTs more affordable than the micro-CTs because the expenses of the use of the medical ones can be covered by public funding, whereas the use of micro-CT scanning frequently depends on private funding; at least this is the case in most countries (Smilg 2017; Wang et al. 2018; Shakeri-Zadeh 2019; López-Rey Pérez et al. 2021; López-Rey Pérez et al. 2022);
- 2) micro-tomographers are also expensive devices to afford, and institutions from developing countries cannot usually achieve them.

Comparison between classical histology and X-ray based methods when studying the costal skeleton.

In these terms, there is an obvious growing interest in the study of the internal anatomy of the costal skeleton, which is demanding the use of X-ray-based techniques to study biological, functional, or even phylogenetic aspects of the costal skeleton (Latimer et al. 2016; Holcombe et al. 2019; Beresheim et al. 2020; López-Rey Pérez et al. 2022). However, we do not know how comparable medical-CT and micro-CT are relative to classical histological techniques. Besides, previous research has shown that rib size changes considerably through the thorax ontogeny, getting its final size like around 14-16 yearas old (Bastir et al. 2013; García-Martínez et al. 2016a; García-Martínez et al. 2017; Lois Zlolski et al. 2019; García-Martínez et al. 2020b) and we do not know if the information obtained using different X-ray-based methods can be extrapolated also to subadult specimens because of a bias in the resolution of the device relative to specimen size. We assess this issue by studying the % Min. Ar. of the rib cross-section, which is a variable that can be informative about biomechanical, taxonomical, and even phylogenetic properties of the costal skeleton.

Our results show that there are important statistical differences in the % Min. Ar. depending on the X-ray method used for the quantification. First of all, its is important to state that the HD resolution micro-CT (between 9–17 microns) provides very similar results to the ones obtained using classical histology sine we do not find statistical evidence for the slight observed between them (Table 3). It is true that to get the high resolution necessary to make comparable micro-CT and histology, the focal detector distance (FDD) should be 42.35 (in our case), and this very short focal distance can be considered as a potential limitation when large specimen aims to be scanned. Then the differences between classical histology become more evident and statistically significant as we low down the resolution, specifically in SDmicro-CT (90 microns) and medical-CT (0.66 mm),

respectively (Table 3). All of the three techniques over-estimate the amount of mineral area in the rib cross-section, which is consistent with recent research from (Schmidutz et al. 2021), who found that micro-CT scanning methods have that kind of limitations to study some cortical bone parameters.

Last but not least, it is important to highlight that micro-CT is useful to address any ontogenetic stage of the thoracic development, but standard medical-CT is only useful when studying late ontogeny (juveniles onwards), which is obviously related to the size of the cross-sectional area and the resolution (Tables 3 and 4).

Limitations for the study

We are aware that the sample size could be considered a potential limitation of our study but, even though X-ray data is relatively easier to obtain, histological methods are destructive and highly time-consuming, which limits sample size. We acknowledge that this kind of study does not replace but complement previous studies using histological techniques, and we are aware that despite the advantages of using CT-based methods for studies on % Min. Ar. as an approach of bone density, distinguishing between the different types of microstructures (osteons, etc.), that are usually identified in the transmitted light microscope by the effect of birefringence, becomes a challenge. Future studies should also compare micro-CT techniques with nano-CT to get higher resolution.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first ontogenetic study that addresses rib ontogeny combining X-ray-based methods with histological techniques. This study opens the window for wider studies on the comparison of different acquisition methods to study the internal rib anatomy, and to studies on ontogeny, sexual dimorphism, biomechanics, or even evolution combining different acquisition methods.

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Topic 6: The use of multi-element and heavy metal analysis to infer the route of transhumance herds (in progress)

Work 11: Detection of heavy metals in the internal structure of ovicaprid teeth from the Castillejo de Bonete site (Ciudad Real)

Access offered : Uranium Series Lab. Research Center on Human Evolution (CENIEH). Burgos, Spain.

Joint UCM-ISCIH Center on Human Evolution and Behavior. Madrid, Spain

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Introduction

The incorporation of elements such as heavy metals in soft and bone tissues of ungulates has long been used as a bio indicator of environmental pollution (Sawicka-Kapusta 1979; Maňková et al., 2012; Demesko et al., 2018). All calcified tissues incorporate the heavy metals to which they are exposed in their mineral phase during their development. Hard tissues of teeth confer an advantage over soft tissues because these heavy metals, once incorporated, remain fixed to their structure without any modification occurring (Gdula-Argasińska et al., 2004). Thus, an accurate historical record of the exposure of animals to various elements is preserved in the calcified tissues of teeth and, therefore, teeth appear to be the most suitable long-term bioindicator of environmental exposure.

However, other information of an archaeological nature can be extracted from the internal structure of teeth in domestic animals, since the incorporation of elements into these tissues occurs through dietary exposure (Gdula-Argasińska et al., 2004) and, therefore, it is possible to make correlations between grazing areas and the elemental content of animal remains.

In the case of the ovicaprids from Castillejo de Bonete, it is hypothesized that, during the transhumance periods, the Chalcolithic and Bronze Age shepherds would make a route through the Alcudia Valley, crossing several lead and mercury mines (such as the well-known Almadén Mine), and these elements would be incorporated into the tissues of the animals when grazing in the surroundings.

Figures 44 Ovicaprid teeth

Objectives and methodology of the study

The main objective of this research is to test if the transhumance of the prehistoric shepherds of the Castillejo de Bonete site crossed the lead and mercury mines of the Alcludia Valley.

To this end, and as a secondary objective, a new method of analysis is being developed to determine the content of these heavy metals in the crystalline structure of several teeth of fossil sheep ovicaprids and to see patterns of incorporation throughout their growth. Twelve teeth from different archaeological levels distributed in the different galleries of the burial mound to study the distribution of the specimens in the site.

In order to verify that the results obtained in relation to the elemental contents are valid, we have used, as a comparison, teeth from two modern sheep, one from the same study area, and the other from the province of Guadalajara. In the first case, the specimen was found in the area near the mining zone of the Alcludia Valley, where the soils are supposed to be enriched in heavy metals and we estimate that the teeth will give a similar signal to that of the fossil sheep. In the second case, the grazing areas do not include any type of mining or anthropic activity that could contribute heavy metals to the dental tissues of this animal.

Geological samples have also been taken from the mining areas near the site to compare the concentration and distribution of heavy metals between sediments and rocks and fossil dental tissues.

The results are in the process of being obtained and the final processing of the data is scheduled for the end of this November.

Analysis protocol

The analysis consisted of the measurement, by means of different spectrometers, of the elemental content in Hg and Pb, mainly in the dentin and enamel of the selected teeth, although other elements will also be measured to complement the study (i.e. U, Th, Sr, Mg).

Figure 45 Process in the laboratory

To perform the analyses, both tissues were mechanically separated using a dentist's microdrill and ground to facilitate their chemical preparation. Approximately 100 mg of each tissue was obtained per tooth analyzed. Each sample was subjected to a chemical digestion process with acid treatment for separation of compounds and removal of unwanted residues.

Figure 46 Process in the laboratory

The samples were digested in 9 mL of HNO₃ to which 1 mL of H₂O₂ was added to remove the organic matter content a C Mars 6 microwave, applying a heating ramp up to 250°C.

Figure 47 A spectrum of lead, the four peaks on the left, showing their natural isotopic abundances. The peak of 209 is bismuth, used as an internal standard. The concentration of lead in this solution was 0.5 parts per billion (0.5 ng.g⁻¹)

Limitations and advantages of the protocol

The use of microwave equipment offers a shorter sample digestion time compared to the traditional heating plate procedure. In addition, the digestion conditions for each sample are the same throughout the whole process, therefore, it is possible to ensure a high repeatability of the results obtained.

On the other hand, there is a slight risk of overpressure in the vials, which implies the risk of losing some of the samples, although this limitation is lower than in hot plate digestion, where the samples can splash with the heating and contaminate each other.

Future prospects

Although the final results have not yet been completed, the next steps of this research will be to perform an analysis on dental tissues by laser ablation coupled to high-resolution spectrometry (LA-ICPMS).

The main objective of this second stage of the project is to sample each tooth at higher resolution by performing analyses spaced every few mm along the growth of the teeth in order to observe annual or even seasonal variations in the mobility of these pastoral populations.

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Topic 7: Development of methodology for EPR characterization of burned bones and determination of temperature to which the bones were exposed to by reflection FTIR and EPR

Work 12 Report on EPR study of burned bovine bones and example of application of the method with complementary FTIR analysis, to determine the burn temperatures of archaeological samples.

Access offered : EPR spectrometers . Institute for the Protection of Cultural Heritage of Slovenia (ZVKDS). Ljubljana, Slovenja.

Authors: Polona Ropret, Lea Legan and Tilen Knaflic.

1 Concept

This study follows in the footsteps of previous work by Legan et al. [1], where an extensive Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy research on burned bovine bone samples was done in order to determine the burn temperature of archaeological bones. Here we present a report on complementary electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) study on the same samples and the suggested methodology on how to use the EPR results to determine the burn temperatures of archaeological bones. In conjunction with FTIR, this is used to determine the burn temperature of an archaeological sample.

2 Case of study-model system

The model system consisted of bovine bones samples, burned at 300 °C, 600 °C, 900 °C and 1200 °C for different amount of time. The details of the samples are presented in Table 12:

T [°C]	30 min	60 min	90 min		120 min
300	S2 (b)	S3 (b)	S4 (b)		S5 (b)
600	S6 (b)	S7 (bg)	S8 (bg)		S9 (bg)
900	S10 (bw)	S11 (gw)	S12 (gw)		S13 (w)
1200	S14 (bw)	S15 (bwr)	S16 (wr)		S17 wr

Table 12 Sample labels with respect to their burn conditions (burn time and temperature). In the parentheses next to the labels are letters, describing the different colours of the sample (b - black, g- gray, w - white and r - rose). The raw (unheated) sample is labelled S1.

3 Protocol

For the purpose of this study, we used the same samples that were studied previously by Legan et al. [1]. Bovine femur was defleshed and cut to 17 pieces of size 4.5 cm X 4 cm. 16 samples of bone were then exposed to different burn conditions, regarding temperature and time of exposure, one was left as a reference (Table 12). Small pieces of the bone were broken away and inserted into the EPR quartz sample tube with regards to their color, so each bone sample could contribute up to three samples for EPR measurements. Room temperature X-band EPR measurements were done using the benchtop EPR spectrometer Bruker EMXnano with microwave frequency of 9.63 GHz.

For selected samples, additional low-temperature measurements between room temperature and 4 K were conducted in the EPR laboratory at the Jožef Stefan Institute (Ljubljana, Slovenia) using a Bruker Elexsys E580 X-band spectrometer operating at 9.37 GHz and equipped with a Varian TEM104 dual-cavity resonator, Oxford Instruments ESR900 cryostat and an Oxford Instruments ITC503 temperature controller with temperature stability better than 0.05 K.

Reflection FTIR analyses on archaeological bones were carried out using a portable Bruker ALPHA-R spectrometer, equipped with a dedicated reflection module, which allows contactless and non-destructive FTIR analysis with a room-temperature deuterated L-alanine-doped triglycine sulfate (DLATGS) detector and a 25°/25° optical layout.

We observed that based on the colour of the samples and their burn temperature, we obtain different EPR spectra (Figure 46). The EPR spectra of burned bones thus originate from carbon-based radicals, Mn^{2+} ions or different carbonate ions. Carbon-based radicals' EPR spectra are centred close to $g = 2$ values and have a narrow EPR linewidth [Figure 46 (a)] [2-5]. They are more pronounced at lower burn temperatures, and their intensity diminishes strongly or even completely vanishes at higher burn temperatures [5]. The manganese EPR signals can be detected in two forms, originating either from the case where manganese is doped in hydroxyapatite [6,7], or when it substitutes calcium in $CaCO_3$ [8,9]. The former occurs at slightly lower burn temperatures (~800 °C) as the latter and the EPR spectrum consists of a single broad EPR line [Figure 46 b)], whereas in the case of Mn^{2+} substitution of Ca^{2+} , we observe six equidistant EPR lines, characteristic of the hyperfine interaction of the electron with the manganese nucleus [Figure 46 (c)]. This signal is expected to occur between 900 °C and 1200 °C. Finally, in the same temperature interval, we also observe different contributions of carbonate ions to the EPR signal, seen as a central complex of lines shown in Figure 46 (c) and (d).

Figure 48 Examples of EPR spectra of the bone samples: (a-top) sample S1 - raw (unheated) bone, (a-bottom) sample S5 (black) - burned for 120 min at 300 °C, (c) gray samples samples S9 (120 min, 600 °C), S11 (60 min, 900 °C) and S12 (90 min, 900 °C), (c) White sample S13 (120 min, 900 °C). Marked with six arrows is the EPR signal of Mn²⁺. (d) EPR spectra of white parts of the bone of sample S11 measured at 4 K (black line), fitted by a three-component powder spectrum simulation with g-factor anisotropy (red line).

Detection of these different types of EPR signals can therefore help us determine the burn temperature of the bones. Additionally, in the case of carbon-based radicals, we also observe a characteristic temperature dependence of the *g*-factor, which is monotonically decreasing with increasing burn temperature. This enables us to extrapolate the burn temperature of the bone samples, which show carbon-based radicals' EPR signals, by measuring the *g*-factor and comparing it to the model shown in Figure 49.

Figure 49 Dependence of g-factor values on the burn temperature. Black circles represent data from black parts of the bone and grey circles from the grey parts of the bone. The red circles are the average g-factor values at a given burn temperature. The solid red line is a linear fit to the average g-factor values, which can serve us as a tool to determine the burn temperature of bones with carbon-based radicals EPR signals.

Following the development of the EPR methodology for the determination of the burn temperature of bones, we determined the burn temperature of the archaeological burned bone fragment, with additional support from the FTIR analysis. Burned bone fragment was excavated at a site in Drnovo of southeast Slovenia [inset in Figure 49 (c)]. The bone fragment labelled L5 from location 8-SE19, shows a wide Lorentzian line at $g = 2.02$ and EPR linewidth of 77 mT, together with the 6 lines of Mn^{2+} , but without the central set of lines of carbonate radicals [Figure 49 (a)]. Instead, only a single isotropic line, centred at $g = 2.0025$ and with the EPR linewidth of 0.34 mT, is most probably of carbon radical origin [Figure 48 (b)]. The g -factor and linewidth values put the burn temperature at around 900 °C, which is also in line with the detected manganese signals. The complementary FTIR analysis shows specific absorption maximums at 1549, 1447 and 1412 cm^{-1} indicating the B-type substitution, i.e. the replacement of the phosphate group with the carbonate group in the lattice of hydroxyapatite [Figure 49 (c)]. Spectral features, which arise due to diffuse reflection contribution (i.e. detection of cyanamidapatite, formation of retained CO_2 , Mg-OH, Cl-OH and 1st overtone of OH stretching vibrations) indicate that the L5 bone fragment was burned at around 900 °C which is consistent with the EPR results.

Figure 50: EPR and reflection FTIR spectra of an archaeological bone, excavated at Drnovo in southeast of Slovenia from location 8-SE19, sample labelled L5. (a) EPR spectra over a wide magnetic field range, showing a broad EPR line with additional seven narrow resonances. The broad line is a characteristic signal for Mn^{2+} doped in hydroxyapatite. (b) EPR spectra over a narrow magnetic field range, showing the additional seven narrow resonances in more detail. The six equidistant resonances are a characteristic EPR signal of Mn^{2+} , when it substitutes calcium in $CaCO_3$. (c) Reflection FTIR spectrum collected on location L5. The asterisk indicates inverted band. The inset shows the image of the measured sample.

4 Protocol limitations and advances

The protocol for determining the burn temperature of bones is mostly limited by the fact that parts of the bone must be broken away in order to fit into the EPR sample tube. This damages the original archaeological artefact and in some cases, this can not be done. Otherwise, the EPR technique is non destructive, as the broken-away part of the sample remains unchanged. Another limitation is also the unpredictability of the accuracy of the determined burn temperature. In some cases, we can get a burn temperature estimate with an error around 100 °C or even less (which is pretty good), however we can stumble on a case where we get a mixture of EPR signals, where one

component shows very different burn temperature than another. The problem lies in the sampling of the artefact, where by breaking away parts of the bone sample, we can unintentionally mix up parts of the bone, which were exposed to different temperatures. In most common cases, this can include parts deep inside the bone, and parts at the surface. So extra care must be taken when preparing the samples. The advantage is that the technique is very easy to use and relatively fast and with the established model and protocol, one can pretty quickly and easily determine the burn temperatures of bones.

5 Perspectives on future directions

In the future, we would like to extend this study to include pulsed EPR technique, as it turns out that the carbon-based radicals show good spin echo signal. With this technique, more precise information of the radicals' local environment can be obtained, which can give us even more precise information on the bone burn temperature.

6 Access Offered

Upon reasonable request, access to EPR spectrometers can be arranged, measurements conducted and help on analysis and interpretation offered.

7 Conclusions

The study presented a comprehensive Electron Paramagnetic Resonance (EPR) analysis on burned bovine bone samples, which were previously studied using Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy. The aim was to determine the burn temperatures of archaeological bones. The EPR spectra varied based on the color of the samples and their burn temperature, indicating the presence of different radicals and ions. By applying the developed EPR methodology on an archaeological burned bone sample, together with a complementary FTIR spectroscopy analysis we were able to obtain a good burn temperature estimate.

This study suggests that EPR, in conjunction with FTIR spectroscopy, can be a powerful tool for determining the burn temperature of archaeological samples. In the future further research with included pulsed EPR spectroscopy, we will be able to refine the methodology and validate these findings across a broader range of sample types and conditions. This could open up new avenues for archaeological research and provide valuable insights into past civilizations and their practices.

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Topic 8: Non-destructive compositional and imaging studies with neutron techniques

Work 13: Non-destructive compositional and imaging studies with neutron techniques

Access Offered: Prompt-gamma activation analysis (PGAA) and neutron imaging (RAD)
Department Centre for Energy Research, (ATOMKI). Budapest, Hungary

Authors: Zsolt Kasztovszky et al.

Prompt-gamma activation analysis (PGAA) proved to be a very effective non-invasive tool in Heritage Science, applicable to study the bulk-representative elemental composition of fossils, various archaeological stone objects and their raw materials. Using appropriate standard reference materials (SRMs), we have investigated the analysis workflow and the individual cases of discriminating elements that are relevant to Heritage Science and routinely measured at the Budapest PGAA laboratory. Geological SRMs representing the raw materials of stone tool manufacturing have been studied. With this work, we aim to corroborate the position of PGAA, as an indispensable part of the Heritage Science toolkit (Kasztovszky et al. 2022).

Although several other well-established analytical methods, such as ICP-AES, ICP-MS, or INAA, have much higher sensitivities, PGAA still has some unique features. The most important advantage of PGAA is the non-destructivity. Thanks to the relatively low intensities of the external neutron beams, long-lived radioactivity is not induced, so the samples reach the legal clearance levels already after a few hours or days of cooling. Unlike in INAA, the sample can be passed on to further analysis or returned to the owner. Secondly, the analysis does not require time-consuming and expensive sample preparation (e.g., dissolution, smelting), the object can be placed into the external beam without any limitations in its dimensions. The other key advantage of PGAA is the high volumetric representativeness of the results. The use of bulk compositional data allows us to avoid any potential bias related to surface alteration of objects, which may occur due to long-term interaction with the environment, and the undisturbed bulk composition can be directly compared to the relevant geological materials.

As in most cases, the bulk compositions of various rocks are characteristic for their place of formation and are not affected significantly by the interaction with the environment after utilisation, one can perform a successful provenance study of stone objects, based exclusively on their major components (Figs 49 and 50).

In the last 25 years, we have performed hundreds of PGAA experiments for provenance research of stone tools made of obsidian, silex and porphyry and various metamorphic rocks. (Kasztovszky et al 1998, Szakmány & Kasztovszky 2004, T. Biró & Kasztovszky 2018, Kasztovszky et al 2018). The

research has been continued also in the frame of the TNA projects of the IPERION HS, the evaluations of the results are in progress

Fig. 51

Fig. 52

Figure 51 Detection limits for the Budapest PGAA in comparison with the typical concentration ranges in the investigated obsidian samples and the JR-1 and JR-2 geological reference materials. Red lines indicate the detection limits of the Budapest PGAA, supposing 1 hour acquisition time. The grey band indicates the minimum and maximum values for 391 obsidian samples. The black dots represent the individual obsidian samples.

Figure 52 Detection limits for the Budapest PGAA in comparison with the typical concentration ranges for the investigated polished stone tool and raw material samples, as well as for JA-1, JA-2, JB-1A, JB-2, and JB-3 geological reference materials. Red lines indicate the detection limits of the Budapest PGAA, supposing 1 hour acquisition time. The grey band indicates the minimum and maximum values for the geological reference samples. The black dots represent the individual polished stone samples, altogether 676 pieces.

The morphological and compositional analysis of fossils provides essential knowledge about the classification and development of the species. For this purpose, we developed a beyond-state-of-the-art combination of three-dimensional surface and volumetric digital imaging techniques, as well as position-resolved element composition analysis (Maróti et al. 2020). We established a methodology to systematically study the 3D shapes and compositions of the specimens so that one could understand the growth of the individuals, the inter- and intraspecific morphological differences. In addition, we can gain information on the conditions of the deposition and fossilization.

To overcome the limitations of X-ray based techniques (technical artifacts in imaging, limited penetration depth in chemical analysis) neutron-based techniques were applied. Besides the visual and morphological appearance, the chemical compositions of the specimens could be characterized. Neutron tomography (NT) can scrutinize the internal structure even of bulky objects of complex internal geometries, especially in case of increased hydrogen contents, giving stronger contrast due to the higher neutron attenuation. Prompt gamma activation analysis (PGAA) is based on the detection of the emitted gamma-rays following the neutron capture. Both neutrons and gamma rays are capable of penetrating several mm-cm thick material. Thus, PGAA provides a reliable and representative bulk chemical composition of the entire irradiated volume.

Neutron-based techniques offer unique opportunities to study the internal structure and composition of palaeontological materials. Those can differentiate lithologies of similar chemistry (e.g. CaCO_3 and CaCO_3 with structural Mn contamination) or similar average Z number (SiO_2 and $\text{Ca}_5(\text{PO}_4)_3\text{OH}$). Thus, recrystallized calcareous fossils in limestone (Fig.3) or bone in siliceous sedimentary rocks (i.e. sandstone) can be localized, analysed and visualized.

Figura 53 . F3D visualization of a fish vertebra inside of a bulky limestone by neutron computed tomography. The stone matrix was made transparent in this rendering to highlight the embedded items of palaeontological relevance, Budapest Neutron Centre, RAD station

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General conclusions and future research lines

The development of the different works carried out are the result of the needs expressed by various researchers in the area related to the topics described and covering fields ranging:

- (i) from Geochronology to achieve the contextualization of fossil records or lithic tools associated with them,
- (ii) image analysis using Microcomputed Tomography and Neutron prompt-gamma Activation analysis techniques and the evaluation of the effect that the use of these techniques can have on the conservation of paleontological and anthropological heritage with the aim of achieving a balance between analysis and conservation that does not compromise the fossil itself and the potential dating by the so-called trapped charge techniques (ESR and OSL).
- (iii) through the development of combined techniques between ESR and FTIR for the determination of the burning temperature of bone and fossil material.

- Several direct and indirect dating techniques have been applied for the contextualization of materials and to obtain minimum ages, demonstrating that the choice of the techniques to be used is fundamental to obtain valid data and that all the geochronological dating possibilities available should be considered, of which CENIEH offers 5 techniques.

- The importance and usefulness of the use of imaging techniques such as computerized microtomography for the study of paleoanthropological materials has been determined, both in highly fossilized materials and in other more modern ones, demonstrating that this technique allows obtaining a great amount of information, to which is added the possibility of using PGAA to simultaneously obtain image and composition of the materials submitted for testing. The combination of both techniques in paleoanthropological studies opens a great field of research to be further explored.

- Good practices have been determined for the scanning of materials by means of microcomputed tomography for the safeguarding of fossil remains and the information they contain, which are currently being applied in CENIEH laboratories. The analysis has highlighted the importance of generating digital collections derived from the various studies carried out by researchers to avoid the repetition of scans.

- The effect of the dose transferred by X-rays to fossil materials has been explored and evaluated, and the effect it can have in order to be able to perform subsequent geochronometric analysis by techniques that use trapped charges as a dating principle. This opens a novel field of research that

goes from the use of Microcomputed Tomography, the PGAA or Sincotron imaging techniques, among others, and that must be evaluated.

- ESR techniques combined with FTIR have been used, showing the potential for the study of taphonomic processes and that it should be further explored and directed to the use of EPR pulse spectroscopy.

- Test equipment has been used for the realization and exploration of taphonomic processes and their analysis by means of 3D microscopy techniques, showing its usefulness to understand processes and opening the possibility to carry out tests that can have an impact on the understanding of the deterioration of paleo-anthropological material, as well as to determine suitable or unsuitable materials for their conservation.

Overview Projects Partners

Abreviation	Institute	Country
CSIC/CENIEH	Centro Nacional de investigación sobre la Evolución Humana	Spain
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Reserche	Italy
ANTECIPA	Federal University of Minas Gerais	France
IPANEMA	Ancient materials research platform	France
CNRS/MNHN,	Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle	France
CSIC/IQFR	Instituto de Química Física Rocasolano	Spain
FORTH	Foundation for Research and Technology – Hellas	Greece
MTA ATOMKI	Institute for Nuclear Research	Hungary
IAA	Israel Antiquities Authority	Israel
UNAM	National Autonomous University of Mexico	Mexico
UIO	University of Oslo	Norway
RAA	Swedish National Heritage Board,	Sweden
ZVKDS	The Institute for the Protection of Cultural Heritage of Slovenia	Slovenia
UCL/NTGU	University College London	UK
GCI	The Getty Conservation Institute	USA
SI MCI	Museum Conservation Institute	USA
KIK-IRPA	Koninklijk Instituut voor het Kunstpatrimonium	BELGIUM
UFMG	Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais	Brazil
Cyl	The Cyprus Institute	Cyprus
ITAM	Ustav Teoreticke a Aplikovane	Czechia
SPK	Stiftung Preussischer Kulturbesitz	Germany
CSIC	Agencia Estatal Consejo superior de Investigaciones Cientificas	Spain
RCE	Ministerie Van Onderwijs Cultuur en Wetwenschap	Netherlands
NCU	Uniwersytet Mikolaja Kopernika W Toruniu	Poland
UCPH	Kobenhavns Universitet	Denmark